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Causal inference and study design

Research article

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Abstract

Background:

Causal inference based on logically consistent mathematical methods requires suitable, high-quality data and a corresponding study design. However, the question of which aspects need a design of a study to consider in order to ensure the possibility to detect cause-effect relationships remains so far unanswered.

Methods:

In this article, we focus on the mathematical requirements of a study design of experimental or non-experimental studies whose aim is to identify causal relationship between events.

Results:

A relatively new proof of the relationship between study design and the possibility of causal inference has been provided. The possible relationship between relative risk, odds ratio and causality has been worked out.

Conclusion:

The mathematical proof described here is of use to improve the study design of experimental and non-experimental studies.

Keywords: Necessary condition; *Conditio sine qua non*; Cause; Effect; Causation; Study design

1. Introduction

Causation(Barukčić, 1989, 1997, 2005, 2016b, 2017a,c, 2021d, Thompson, 2006) is an essential concept in science, and more particularly in clinical medical research. In clinical medical research, many times, causality is demonstrated by an experiment or better to say by a randomized controlled trial¹ (RCT). Out of the wide variety of reasons, often, an RCT cannot be conducted. Thus far, under conditions when an experiment cannot be conducted, an observational study need to be performed.

¹Bland JM, Kerry SM. Statistics notes. Trials randomised in clusters. *BMJ*. 1997 Sep 6;315(7108):600. doi: 10.1136/bmj.315.7108.600. PMID: 9302962; PMCID: PMC2127388.

There are a number of different methods ^{2 3} which attempt to infer causality ^{4 , 5} from experimental and non-experimental or observational data. However, these methods ^{6 , 7 , 8} differ extremely and are highly unreliable, especially in the absence of experimental data. Taken into account the planning of a study, often the difficulties to infer a causal relationship between events increase. Many times, the study design of (medical) studies is inappropriate because the prerequisites of a correct study design are not applied strictly enough or completely ignored, while the conclusion drawn by methods ⁹ used to demonstrate a causal relationship under these circumstances are in vain. Such circumstances might provoke some unjustified confusion about a natural concept of causation. Nonetheless, a far-reaching and much more difficult question is, what are the prerequisites of a correct study design ^{10 , 11 , 12 , 13 , 14} and can causality ¹⁵ be defined or demonstrated by medical studies at all, and to what extent? The methods developed here can be used to derive causal inferences from experimental or non-experimental (observational) studies.

²Snow J. Cholera and the Water Supply in the South Districts of London in 1854. *J Public Health Sanit Rev.* 1856 Oct;2(7):239-257. PMID: 30378891; PMCID: PMC6004154.

³Grimes DA, Schulz KF. Bias and causal associations in observational research. *Lancet.* 2002 Jan 19;359(9302):248-52. doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(02)07451-2. PMID: 11812579.

⁴Bach JF. Causality in medicine. *C R Biol.* 2019 Mar-May;342(3-4):55-57. doi: 10.1016/j.crvi.2019.03.001. Epub 2019 Apr 10. PMID: 30981720.

⁵Kamangar F. Causality in epidemiology. *Arch Iran Med.* 2012 Oct;15(10):641-7. PMID: 23020541.

⁶Sir Bradford Hill A. The environment and disease: association or causation? *Proc R Soc Med.* 1965 May;58(5):295-300. PMID: 14283879; PMCID: PMC1898525.

⁷Dekkers OM. The long and winding road to causality. *Eur J Epidemiol.* 2019 Jun;34(6):533-535. doi: 10.1007/s10654-019-00507-4. PMID: 30887378; PMCID: PMC6497614.

⁸Olsen J, Jensen UJ. Causal criteria: time has come for a revision. *Eur J Epidemiol.* 2019 Jun;34(6):537-541. doi: 10.1007/s10654-018-00479-x. Epub 2019 Jan 16. PMID: 30649703.

⁹Parascandola M, Weed DL. Causation in epidemiology. *J Epidemiol Community Health.* 2001 Dec;55(12):905-12. doi: 10.1136/jech.55.12.905. PMID: 11707485; PMCID: PMC1731812.

¹⁰Estrada S, Arancibia M, Stojanova J, Papuzinski C. General concepts in biostatistics and clinical epidemiology: Experimental studies with randomized clinical trial design. *Medwave.* 2020 Apr 8;20(3):e7869. Spanish, English. doi: 10.5867/medwave.2020.02.7869. PMID: 32469850. Format:

¹¹Lazcano G, Papuzinski C, Madrid E, Arancibia M. General concepts in biostatistics and clinical epidemiology: observational studies with cohort design. *Medwave.* 2019 Dec 16;19(11):e7748. Spanish, English. doi: 10.5867/medwave.2019.11.7748. PMID: 31999676.

¹²Martínez D, Papuzinski C, Stojanova J, Arancibia M. General concepts in biostatistics and clinical epidemiology: observational studies with case-control design. *Medwave.* 2019 Nov 7;19(10):e7716. Spanish, English. doi: 10.5867/medwave.2019.10.7716. PMID: 31821315.

¹³Barraza F, Arancibia M, Madrid E, Papuzinski C. General concepts in biostatistics and clinical epidemiology: Random error and systematic error. *Medwave.* 2019 Aug 27;19(7):e7687. Spanish, English. doi: 10.5867/medwave.2019.07.7687. PMID: 31584929.

¹⁴Cataldo R, Arancibia M, Stojanova J, Papuzinski C. General concepts in biostatistics and clinical epidemiology: Observational studies with cross-sectional and ecological designs. *Medwave.* 2019 Sep 25;19(8):e7698. Spanish, English. doi: 10.5867/medwave.2019.08.7698. PMID: 31596838.

¹⁵Susser M. What is a cause and how do we know one? A grammar for pragmatic epidemiology. *Am J Epidemiol.* 1991 Apr 1;133(7):635-48. doi: 10.1093/oxfordjournals.aje.a115939. PMID: 2018019.

2. Material and methods

Scientific knowledge and objective reality are deeply interrelated. Seen by light, grey is never merely simply grey, and many paths may lead to climb up a certain mountain. In the following of this paper, we will reanalyse the relationship between oxygen and human survival in many ways and under different circumstances to reach the main goal.

2.1. Methods

Definitions should help us to provide and assure a systematic approach to a mathematical formulation of the relationship of a necessary condition. It also goes without the need of further saying that a definition must be logically consistent and correct.

2.1.1. Random variables

Let a **random variable**(Gosset, 1914) X denote something like a function defined on a probability space, which itself maps from the sample space(Neyman and Pearson, 1933) to the real numbers.

2.1.2. The Expectation of a Random Variable

Definition 2.1 (The First Moment Expectation of a Random Variable). *Summaries of an entire distribution of a random variable(see Kolmogorov, Andreï Nikolaevich, 1950, p. 22) X , such as the expected value, or average value, are useful in order to identify where X is expected to be without describing the entire distribution. For practical and other reasons, we shall limit ourselves here to discrete random variables, while the basic properties of the expectation value of a random variable X will not be investigated. Thus far, let X be a discrete random variable with the probability $p(X)$. The first moment expectation value (see Huygens and van Schooten, 1657, Kolmogorov, Andreï Nikolaevich, 1950, LaPlace, 1812, Whitworth, 1901) of X , denoted by $E(X)$, is a number defined as follows:*

$$E(X) \equiv p(X) \times X \quad (1)$$

The first moment expectation value squared of a random variable X follows as

$$\begin{aligned} E(X)^2 &\equiv p(X) \times X \times p(X) \times X \\ &\equiv p(X) \times p(X) \times X \times X \\ &\equiv (p(X) \times X)^2 \\ &\equiv E(X) \times E(X) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Definition 2.2 (The Second Moment Expectation of a Random Variable). *The second(see Kolmogorov, Andreï Nikolaevich, 1950, p. 42) moment expectation value (or more or less arithmetic*

mean) of a (large) number of independent realizations of a random variable X follows as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(X^2) &\equiv p(X) \times X^2 \\
 &\equiv (p(X) \times X) \times X \\
 &\equiv E(X) \times X \\
 &\equiv X \times E(X)
 \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

Definition 2.3 (The n-th Moment Expectation of a Random Variable). The n-th (see [Barukčić, 2020a, 2021d](#)) moment expectation value of a (large) number of independent realizations of a random variable X follows as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(X^n) &\equiv p(X) \times X^n \\
 &\equiv (p(X) \times X) \times X^{n-1} \\
 &\equiv E(X) \times X^{n-1}
 \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

2.1.3. Probability of a Random Variable

The probability $p(X)$ of a random variable X follows as (see equation 1)

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(X) &\equiv \frac{X \times p(X)}{X} \equiv \frac{E(X)}{X} \\
 &\equiv \frac{X \times X \times p(X)}{X \times X} \equiv \frac{E(X^2)}{X^2} \\
 &\equiv \frac{E(X) \times E(X)}{E(X) \times X} \equiv \frac{E(X)^2}{E(X^2)} \\
 &\equiv \Psi(X) \times \Psi^*(X)
 \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

where $\Psi(X)$ is the wave-function of X , $\Psi^*(X)$ is the complex conjugate wave-function of X .

2.1.4. Variance of a Random Variable

Definition 2.4 (The Variance of a Random Variable). *Johann Carl Friedrich Gauß (1777-1855) introduced the normal distribution and the error of mean squared in his 1809 monograph (see [Gauß, Carl Friedrich, 1809](#)). In the following, Karl Pearson (1857-1936) coined the term “standard deviation” in 1893. Pearson is writing: “Then σ will be termed its standard-deviation (error of mean square).” (see [Pearson, 1894](#), p. 80). Finally, the term variance was introduced by Sir Ronald Aylmer Fisher (1890-1962) in the year 1918.*

*“The ... deviations of a ... measurement from its mean ... may be ... measured by the standard deviation corresponding to the square root of the mean square error ... It is ... desirable **in analysing the causes** ... to deal with the square of the standard deviation as the measure of variability. We shall term this quantity the Variance...”*

(see [Fisher, Ronald Aylmer, 1919](#), p. 399)

The deviation of a random variable X from its population mean or sample mean $E(X)$ has a central role in statistics and is one important measure of dispersion. The variance $\sigma(X)^2$ (see [Kolmogorov, Andreï Nikolaevich, 1950](#), p. 42), the second central moment of a distribution, is the expectation value of the squared deviation of a random variable X from its own expectation value $E(X)$ and is determined in general as (see equation 3):

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sigma(X)^2 &\equiv E(X^2) - E(X)^2 \\
 &\equiv (X \times E(X)) - E(X)^2 \\
 &\equiv E(X) \times (X - E(X)) \\
 &\equiv E(X) \times E(\underline{X})
 \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

while $E(\underline{X}) \equiv X - E(X)$. In particular, variance is a specific statistical method which is of help to evaluate hypotheses in the light of empirical facts. But as a mathematical tool or method, variance is also a science specific description of a certain part of objective reality. In this context, as a general mathematical principle, one fundamental meaning of variance is to provide a link between something and its own other.

“The variance in this sense is a measure of the inner contradictions of a random variable, of changes, of struggle within this random variable itself, or the greater $\sigma(X)^2$ of a random variable, the greater the inner contradictions of this random variable.”

(see [Barukčić, 2006a](#), p. 57)

All things considered, we can safely say that, on the whole, **the variance is a mathematical description of the philosophical notion of the inner contradiction of a random variable X** (see [Hegel](#),

Georg Wilhelm Friedrich, 1812, 1813, 1816) . Based on equation 6, it is

$$E(X^2) \equiv E(X)^2 + \sigma(X)^2 \quad (7)$$

or

$$\frac{E(X)^2}{E(X^2)} + \frac{\sigma(X)^2}{E(X^2)} \equiv p(X) + \frac{\sigma(X)^2}{E(X^2)} \equiv +1 \quad (8)$$

In other words, the variance (see Barukčić, 2006b) of a random variable is a determining part of the probability of a random variable. The wave function Ψ follows in general, as

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi(X) &\equiv \frac{1}{\Psi^*(X)} - \frac{\sigma(X)^2}{(\Psi^*(X) \times E(X^2))} \\ &\equiv \frac{(E(X^2) - \sigma(X)^2)}{(\Psi^*(X) \times E(X^2))} \\ &\equiv \frac{1}{(\Psi^*(X) \times E(X^2))} \times (E(X^2) - \sigma(X)^2) \\ &\equiv \frac{1}{(\Psi^*(X) \times E(X^2))} \times E(X)^2 \\ &\equiv \frac{1}{\Psi^*(X)} \times \frac{E(X)^2}{E(X^2)} \\ &\equiv \frac{1}{\Psi^*(X) \times X} \times E(X) \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

The wave function (see Born, 1926) of a quantum-mechanical system is a central determining part of the Schrödinger wave equation (see Schrödinger, Erwin Rudolf Josef Alexander, 1926, 1929, 1952).

Definition 2.5 (The First Moment Expectation of a Random Variable of \underline{X} (anti X)). In general, let $E(\underline{X})$ be defined as

$$E(\underline{X}) \equiv X - E(X) \equiv X - (X \times p(X)) \quad (10)$$

and denote an expectation value of a (discrete) random variable anti X with the probability

$$p(\underline{X}) \equiv 1 - p(X) \quad (11)$$

The first moment expectation value (see Huygens and van Schooten, 1657, Kolmogorov, Andreï Nikolaevich, 1950, LaPlace, 1812, Whitworth, 1901) of anti X , denoted as $E(\underline{X})$, is a number defined as follows:

$$E(\underline{X}) \equiv X - (X \times p(X)) \equiv X \times (1 - p(X)) \equiv X \times p(\underline{X}) \quad (12)$$

The first moment expectation value squared of a random variable anti X follows as

$$\begin{aligned} E(\underline{X})^2 &\equiv p(\underline{X}) \times X \times p(\underline{X}) \times X \\ &\equiv p(\underline{X}) \times p(\underline{X}) \times X \times X \\ &\equiv (p(\underline{X}) \times X)^2 \\ &\equiv E(\underline{X}) \times E(\underline{X}) \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Definition 2.6 (The Second Moment Expectation of a Random Variable of \underline{X} (anti X)). *The second (see [Kolmogorov, Andrej Nikolaevich, 1950, p. 42](#)) moment expectation value (or more or less arithmetic mean) of a (large) number of independent realizations of a random variable anti X follows as:*

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(\underline{X}^2) &\equiv p(\underline{X}) \times X^2 \\
 &\equiv (p(\underline{X}) \times X) \times X \\
 &\equiv E(\underline{X}) \times X \\
 &\equiv X \times E(\underline{X})
 \end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

Definition 2.7 (The n-th Moment Expectation of a Random Variable of \underline{X} (anti X)). *The n-th (see [Barukčić, 2020a, 2021d](#)) moment expectation value of a (large) number of independent realizations of a random variable anti X follows as:*

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(\underline{X}^n) &\equiv p(\underline{X}) \times X^n \\
 &\equiv (p(\underline{X}) \times X) \times X^{n-1} \\
 &\equiv E(\underline{X}) \times X^{n-1}
 \end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

2.1.5. Bernoulli distribution

A single event distribution is more or less a discrete probability distribution of any random variable X which takes a certain (observer independent) single value X_t at a **Bernoulli trial** (Uspensky, 1937, p. 45) (period of time) t with the probability $p(X_t)$. The same random variable X takes a certain single anti value \underline{X}_t at a Bernoulli trial (period of time) t with the probability $1-p(X_t)$. There are conditions in nature where a random variable X can take only the values either $+0$ or $+1$ (see Birnbaum, 1961). Under these conditions, the random variable X takes the value 1 with probability $p(X_t = +1)$ and the value 0 with probability $q(X_t = +0) = 1 - p(X_t = +1)$ while the single event distribution passes over into the **Bernoulli distribution**, named after Swiss mathematician Jacob Bernoulli (Bernoulli, 1713). Less formally, many times, the Bernoulli distribution is represented by a (possibly not biased) coin toss where 1 and 0 would represent ‘heads’ and ‘tails’ (or vice versa), respectively. However, the relationship between random variables (Gosset, 1914) can be investigated by many (Gosset, 1908) methods, including the tools of probability theory, too.

Definition 2.8 (Two by two table of single event random variables).

The two by two or contingency table which has been introduced by Karl Pearson (Pearson, 1904b) in 1904 harbours still a large variety of topics and debates. Central to this is the problem to apply the laws of classical logic on data sets, which concerns the justification of inferences which extrapolate from sample data to general facts. Nevertheless, a contingency table is still an appropriate theoretical model too for studying the relationships between random variables, including *Bernoulli* (Bernoulli, 1713) (i.e. $+0/+1$) distributed random variables existing or occurring at the same *Bernoulli trial* (Uspensky, 1937) (period of time) t .

In this context, let a random variable A at the *Bernoulli trial* (Uspensky, 1937) (period of time) t , denoted by A_t , indicate a risk factor, a condition, a cause et cetera and occur or exist with the probability $p(A_t)$ at the *Bernoulli trial* (Uspensky, 1937) (period of time) t . Let $E(A_t)$ denote the expectation value of A_t . In general it is

$$p(A_t) \equiv p(a_t) + p(b_t) \quad (16)$$

The expectation value $E(A_t)$ follows as

$$\begin{aligned} E(A_t) &\equiv A_t \times p(A_t) \\ &\equiv A_t \times (p(a_t) + p(b_t)) \\ &\equiv (A_t \times p(a_t)) + (A_t \times p(b_t)) \\ &\equiv E(a_t) + E(b_t) \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

Under conditions of $+0/+1$ distributed Bernoulli random variables it is

$$\begin{aligned} E(A_t) &\equiv A_t \times p(A_t) \\ &\equiv (+0 + 1) \times p(A_t) \\ &\equiv p(A_t) \\ &\equiv p(a_t) + p(b_t) \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

Furthermore, it is

$$p(\underline{A}_t) \equiv p(c_t) + p(d_t) \equiv (1 - p(A_t)) \quad (19)$$

The expectation value $E(\underline{A}_t)$ is given as

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(\underline{A}_t) &\equiv A_t \times (1 - p(A_t)) \\
 &\equiv A_t \times (p(c_t) + p(d_t)) \\
 &\equiv (A_t \times p(c_t)) + (A_t \times p(d_t)) \\
 &\equiv E(c_t) + E(d_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{20}$$

Under conditions of +0/+1 distributed Bernoulli random variables we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(\underline{A}_t) &\equiv A_t \times (1 - p(A_t)) \\
 &\equiv (+0 + 1) \times (1 - p(A_t)) \\
 &\equiv (1 - p(A_t)) \\
 &\equiv p(c_t) + p(d_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{21}$$

Let a random variable B at the *Bernoulli trial* (Uspensky, 1937) (period of time) t , denoted by B_t , indicate an outcome, a conditioned, an effect et cetera and occur or exist with the probability $p(B_t)$ at the *Bernoulli trial* (Uspensky, 1937) (period of time) t . Let $E(B_t)$ denote the expectation value of B_t . In general it is

$$p(B_t) \equiv p(a_t) + p(c_t) \tag{22}$$

The expectation value $E(B_t)$ is given by the equation

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(B_t) &\equiv B_t \times p(B_t) \\
 &\equiv B_t \times (p(a_t) + p(c_t)) \\
 &\equiv (B_t \times p(a_t)) + (B_t \times p(c_t)) \\
 &\equiv E(a_t) + E(c_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{23}$$

Under conditions of +0/+1 distributed Bernoulli random variables it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(B_t) &\equiv B_t \times p(B_t) \\
 &\equiv (+0 + 1) \times p(B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(a_t) + p(c_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{24}$$

Furthermore, it is

$$p(\underline{B}_t) \equiv p(b_t) + p(d_t) \equiv (1 - p(B_t)) \tag{25}$$

The expectation value $E(\underline{B}_t)$ is given by the equation

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(\underline{B}_t) &\equiv B_t \times (1 - p(B_t)) \\
 &\equiv B_t \times (p(b_t) + p(d_t)) \\
 &\equiv (B_t \times p(b_t)) + (B_t \times p(d_t)) \\
 &\equiv E(b_t) + E(d_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{26}$$

Under conditions of +0/+1 distributed Bernoulli random variables it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(\underline{B}_t) &\equiv B_t \times (1 - p(B_t)) \\
 &\equiv (+0 + 1) \times (1 - p(B_t)) \\
 &\equiv (1 - p(B_t)) \\
 &\equiv p(b_t) + p(d_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{27}$$

Let $p(a_t) = p(A_t \wedge B_t)$ denote the joint probability distribution of A_t and B_t at the same Bernoulli trial (period of time) t . In general, it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(a_t) &\equiv E(A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv (A_t \times B_t) \times p(A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv (A_t \times B_t) \times p(a_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{28}$$

Under conditions of +0/+1 distributed Bernoulli random variables, it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(a_t) &\equiv E(A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv (A_t \times B_t) \times p(A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv ((+0 + 1) \times (+0 + 1)) \times p(A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(a_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{29}$$

Let $p(b_t) = p(A_t \wedge \neg B_t)$ denote the joint probability distribution of A_t and not B_t at the same Bernoulli trial (period of time) t . In general, it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(b_t) &\equiv E(A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv (A_t \times \neg B_t) \times p(A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv (A_t \times \neg B_t) \times p(b_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{30}$$

Under conditions of +0/+1 distributed Bernoulli random variables, it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(b_t) &\equiv E(A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv (A_t \times \neg B_t) \times p(A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv ((+0 + 1) \times (+0 + 1)) \times p(A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(b_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{31}$$

Let $p(c_t) = p(\neg A_t \wedge B_t)$ denote the joint probability distribution of not A_t and B_t at the same Bernoulli trial (period of time) t . In general, it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(c_t) &\equiv E(\neg A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv (\neg A_t \wedge B_t) \times p(\neg A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv (\neg A_t \wedge B_t) \times p(c_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{32}$$

Under conditions of +0/+1 distributed Bernoulli random variables, it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(c_t) &\equiv E(\neg A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv (\neg A_t \times B_t) \times p(\neg A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv ((+0 + 1) \times (+0 + 1)) \times p(\neg A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(\neg A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(c_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{33}$$

Let $p(d_t) = p(\neg A_t \wedge \neg B_t)$ denote the joint probability distribution of not A_t and not B_t at the same Bernoulli trial (period of time) t . In general, it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(d_t) &\equiv E(\neg A_t \times \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv (\neg A_t \times \neg B_t) \times p(\neg A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv (\neg A_t \times \neg B_t) \times p(d_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{34}$$

Under conditions of +0/+1 distributed Bernoulli random variables, it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(d_t) &\equiv E(\neg A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv (\neg A_t \times \neg B_t) \times p(\neg A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv ((+0 + 1) \times (+0 + 1)) \times p(\neg A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(\neg A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(d_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{35}$$

In general, it is

$$p(a_t) + p(b_t) + p(c_t) + p(d_t) \equiv +1 \tag{36}$$

Table 1 provide us with an overview of the definitions above.

Table 1. The two by two table of Bernoulli random variables

		Conditioned B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition A_t	TRUE	$p(a_t)$	$p(b_t)$	$p(A_t)$
	FALSE	$p(c_t)$	$p(d_t)$	$p(\underline{A}_t)$
		$p(B_t)$	$p(\underline{B}_t)$	+1

2.1.6. Binomial random variables

The binomial distribution (see [Cramér, 1937](#)) with parameters n and p has been developed by the Swiss mathematician Jakob Bernoulli (1655-1705) in a proof published in his 1713 book *Ars Conjectandi* (see [Bernoulli, 1713](#)) Part 1. In probability theory and statistics, the probability of getting exactly k successes in n independent Bernoulli trials is given by the probability mass function as

$$p(X_t = k) \equiv \binom{n}{k} \cdot p^k \cdot q^{n-k} \quad (37)$$

is $\binom{n}{k} = \frac{n!}{k!(n-k)!}$ the binomial coefficient while the cumulative distribution function is given as

$$p(X_t \leq k) \equiv 1 - p(X_t > k) \equiv \sum_{t=0}^k \binom{n}{t} \cdot p^t \cdot q^{n-t} \quad (38)$$

or as

$$p(X_t > k) \equiv 1 - p(X_t \leq k) \equiv 1 - \sum_{t=0}^k \binom{n}{t} \cdot p^t \cdot q^{n-t} \quad (39)$$

Furthermore, it is

$$p(X_t < k) \equiv 1 - p(X_t \geq k) \equiv \sum_{t=0}^{k-1} \binom{n}{t} \cdot p^t \cdot q^{n-t} \quad (40)$$

or

$$p(X_t \geq k) \equiv 1 - p(X_t < k) \equiv 1 - \sum_{t=0}^{k-1} \binom{n}{t} \cdot p^t \cdot q^{n-t} \quad (41)$$

The binomial distribution is the mathematical foundation of a binomial test. The random variable X_t is counting for different things. The discrete geometric (see [Feller, 1950](#), p. 61) distribution describes under certain circumstances the number of Bernoulli trials needed to get one success. The probability that the first occurrence of success requires k independent trials, each with success probability p , is given by the equation

$$p(X_t = k) \equiv p \cdot q^{k-1} \quad (42)$$

The negative (see [Fisher, 1941](#), [Haldane, 1941](#)) binomial probability is a discrete probability distribution which defines the number of successes (k) in a sequence of independent and identically distributed Bernoulli trials (n) before a specified (non-random) number of failures (denoted r) occurs. The probability mass function of the negative binomial distribution is

$$p(X_t = r) \equiv \binom{k+r-1}{k-1} p^k \cdot q^r \quad (43)$$

where k is the number of successes, r is the number of failures, and p is the probability of success.

Definition 2.9 (Expectation value and variance of a binomial random variable).

The variance (see [Pearson, 1904a](#), p. 66) of the binomial distribution with parameters n , the number of independent experiments each asking a yes–no question and p , the probability of a single event, is defined in contrast to Pearson (see [Barukčić, Ilija, 2022](#)) as

$$\sigma(X_t)^2 \equiv N \times N \times p(X_t) \times (1 - p(X_t)) \quad (44)$$

Definition 2.10 (Two by two table of Binomial random variables).

Let $a, b, c, d, A, \underline{A}, B,$ and \underline{B} denote expectation values. Under conditions where *the probability of an event, an outcome, a success et cetera is constant from Bernoulli trial to Bernoulli trial t* , it is

$$\begin{aligned} A &= N \times E(A_t) \\ &\equiv N \times (A_t \times p(A_t)) \\ &\equiv N \times (p(A_t) + p(B_t)) \\ &\equiv N \times p(A_t) \end{aligned} \quad (45)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} B &= N \times E(B_t) \\ &\equiv N \times (B_t \times p(B_t)) \\ &\equiv N \times (p(A_t) + p(c_t)) \\ &\equiv N \times p(B_t) \end{aligned} \quad (46)$$

where N might denote the population or even the sample size. Furthermore, it is

$$a \equiv N \times (E(A_t)) \equiv N \times (p(A_t)) \quad (47)$$

and

$$b \equiv N \times (E(B_t)) \equiv N \times (p(B_t)) \quad (48)$$

and

$$c \equiv N \times (E(c_t)) \equiv N \times (p(c_t)) \quad (49)$$

and

$$d \equiv N \times (E(d_t)) \equiv N \times (p(d_t)) \quad (50)$$

and

$$a + b + c + d \equiv A + \underline{A} \equiv B + \underline{B} \equiv N \quad (51)$$

Table 2 provide us again an overview of a two by two table of Binomial random variables.

Table 2. The two by two table of Binomial random variables

		Conditioned B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition A_t	TRUE	a	b	A
	FALSE	c	d	<u>A</u>
		B	<u>B</u>	N

2.1.7. Independence

Definition 2.11 (Independence).

The philosophical, mathematical (Kolmogoroff, Andreï Nikolaevich, 1933) and physical (Einstein, 1948) concept of independence is of fundamental (Kolmogoroff, Andreï Nikolaevich, 1933) importance in (natural) sciences as such. In fact, it is insightful to recall again before the mind's eye Einstein's theoretical approach to the concept of independence. "*Ohne die Annahme einer ... Unabhängigkeit der ... Dinge voneinander ... wäre physikalisches Denken ... nicht möglich.*" (Einstein, 1948). In a narrower sense, the *conditio sine qua non* relationship concerns itself at the end only with the case whether the presence of an event A_t (condition) enables or guarantees the presence of another event B_t (conditioned). As a result of these thoughts, another question worth asking concerns the relationship between the independence of an event A_t (a condition) and another event B_t (conditioned) and the necessary condition relationship. To be confronted with the danger of bias and equally with the burden of inappropriate conclusions drawn, another fundamental question at this stage is whether is it possible that an event A_t (a condition) is a necessary condition of event B_t (conditioned) even under circumstances where the event A_t (a condition) (a necessary condition) is independent of an event B_t (conditioned)? This question is already answered more or less to the negative (Barukčić, 2018b). An event A_t which is a necessary condition of another event B_t is equally an event without which another event (B_t) could not be, could not occur, and implies as such already a kind of dependence. However, it is not mandatory that such a kind of dependence is a causal one. Thus far, **data which provide evidence of a significant *conditio sine qua non* relationship between two events like A_t and B_t and equally support the hypothesis that A_t and B_t are independent of each other are more or less self-contradictory and of very restricted or of none value for further analysis.** In fact, if the opposite view would be taken as plausible, contradictions are more or less inescapable. In general, an event A_t at the Bernoulli trial t need not but can be independent of the existence or of the occurrence of another event B_t at the same Bernoulli trial t . Mathematically (Moivre, 1718), independence (Kolmogoroff, Andreï Nikolaevich, 1933) in terms of probability theory is defined at the same (period of) time (i.e. Bernoulli trial) t as

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(A_t \wedge B_t) &\equiv p(A_t) \times p(B_t) \equiv p(a_t) \\
 &\equiv \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N (A_t \wedge B_t)}{N} \equiv \frac{N \times (p(a_t))}{N} \equiv 1 - p(A_t | B_t) \equiv 1 - p(A_t \uparrow B_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{52}$$

while $p(A_t \cap B_t)$ is the joint probability of the events A_t and B_t at a same Bernoulli trial t , $p(A_t)$ is the probability of an event A_t at a same Bernoulli trial t , and $p(B_t)$ is the probability of an event B_t at a

same Bernoulli trial t .

2.1.8. Dependence

Definition 2.12 (Dependence).

The dependence of events (Barukčić, 1989, p. 57-61) is defined as

$$p \left(\underbrace{A_t \wedge B_t \wedge C_t \wedge \dots}_{n \text{ random variables}} \right) \equiv \sqrt[n]{\underbrace{p(A_t) \times p(B_t) \times p(C_t) \times \dots}_{n \text{ random variables}}} \quad (53)$$

2.1.9. Relative risk (RR)

Relative risk (RR_{nc})

Definition 2.13 (Relative risk (RR_{nc})).

The degree of association between the two binomial variables can be assessed by a number of very different coefficients, the relative (Cornfield, 1951, Sadowsky et al., 1953) risk is one (see Barukčić, 2021c) of them. In general, relative risk RR_{nc} , which provides some evidence of a necessary condition (see Barukčić, 2021c), is defined as

$$\begin{aligned}
 RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc} &\equiv \frac{\frac{p(a_t)}{p(A_t)}}{\frac{p(c_t)}{p(NotA_t)}} \\
 &\equiv \frac{p(a_t) \times p(NotA_t)}{p(c_t) \times p(A_t)} \\
 &\equiv \frac{N \times p(a_t) \times N \times p(NotA_t)}{N \times p(c_t) \times N \times p(A_t)} \\
 &\equiv \frac{a_t \times (NotA_t)}{c_t \times A_t} \\
 &\equiv \frac{EER(A_t, B_t)}{CER(A_t, B_t)}
 \end{aligned} \tag{54}$$

That what scientist generally understand by relative risk is the ratio of a probability of an event occurring with an exposure versus the probability of an event occurring without an exposure. In other words,

relative risk = (probability(event in exposed group)) / (probability(the same event in not exposed group)).

A $RR(A_t, B_t) = +1$ means that exposure does not affect the outcome or both are independent of each other while $RR(A_t, B_t)$ less than +1 means that the risk of the outcome is decreased by the exposure. In this context, an $RR(A_t, B_t)$ greater than +1 denotes that the risk of the outcome is increased by the exposure. Widely known problems with odds ratio and relative risk are already documented in literature.

Relative risk (RR (sc))

Definition 2.14 (Relative risk (RR (sc))).

The relative risk (sc), which provides some evidence of a sufficient (see Barukčić, 2021c) condition,

is calculated from the point of view of an outcome and is defined as

$$\begin{aligned}
 RR(A_t, B_t)_{sc} &\equiv \frac{\frac{p(a_t)}{p(B_t)}}{\frac{p(b_t)}{p(NotB_t)}} \\
 &\equiv \frac{p(a_t) \times p(NotB_t)}{p(b_t) \times p(B_t)} \\
 &\equiv \frac{N \times p(a_t) \times N \times p(NotB_t)}{N \times p(b_t) \times N \times p(B_t)} \\
 &\equiv \frac{a_t \times (NotB_t)}{b_t \times B_t} \\
 &\equiv \frac{OPR(A_t, B_t)}{CPR(A_t, B_t)}
 \end{aligned} \tag{55}$$

Relative risk reduction (RRR)

Definition 2.15 (Relative risk reduction (RRR)).

$$\begin{aligned}
 RRR(A_t, B_t) &\equiv \frac{CER(A_t, B_t) - EER(A_t, B_t)}{CER(A_t, B_t)} \\
 &= 1 - RR(A_t, B_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{56}$$

Vaccine efficacy (VE)

Definition 2.16 (Vaccine efficacy (VE)).

Vaccine efficacy is defined as the percentage reduction of a disease in a vaccinated group of people as compared to an unvaccinated group of people.

$$\begin{aligned}
 VE(A_t, B_t) &\equiv 100 \times (1 - RR(A_t, B_t)) \\
 &\equiv 100 \times \left(\frac{CER(A_t, B_t) - EER(A_t, B_t)}{CER(A_t, B_t)} \right)
 \end{aligned} \tag{57}$$

Historically, vaccine efficacy has been designed to evaluate the efficacy of a certain vaccine by Greenwood and Yule in 1915 for the cholera and typhoid vaccines (Greenwood and Yule, 1915) and best measured using double-blind, randomized, clinical controlled trials. However, the calculated vaccine efficacy is depending too much on the study design, can lead to erroneous conclusions and is only of very limited value.

Experimental event rate (EER)

Definition 2.17 (Experimental event rate (EER)).

$$EER(A_t, B_t) \equiv \frac{p(a_t)}{p(A_t)} = \frac{a_t}{a_t + b_t} \quad (58)$$

Definition 2.18 (Control event rate (CER)).

$$CER(A_t, B_t) \equiv \frac{p(c_t)}{p(\underline{A}_t)} = \frac{c_t}{c_t + d_t} \quad (59)$$

Absolute risk reduction (ARR)

Definition 2.19 (Absolute risk reduction (ARR)).

$$\begin{aligned} ARR(A_t, B_t) &\equiv \frac{p(c_t)}{p(\underline{A}_t)} - \frac{p(a_t)}{p(A_t)} \\ &= \frac{c_t}{c_t + d_t} - \frac{a_t}{a_t + b_t} \\ &= CER(A_t, B_t) - EER(A_t, B_t) \end{aligned} \quad (60)$$

Absolute risk increase (ARI)

Definition 2.20 (Absolute risk increase (ARI)).

$$\begin{aligned} ARI(A_t, B_t) &\equiv \frac{p(a_t)}{p(A_t)} - \frac{p(c_t)}{p(\underline{A}_t)} \\ &= EER(A_t, B_t) - CER(A_t, B_t) \end{aligned} \quad (61)$$

Number needed to treat (NNT)

Definition 2.21 (Number needed to treat (NNT)).

$$NNT(A_t, B_t) \equiv \frac{1}{CER(A_t, B_t) - EER(A_t, B_t)} \quad (62)$$

An ideal number needed to treat (Cook and Sackett, 1995, Laupacis et al., 1988), mathematically the reciprocal of the absolute risk reduction, is $NNT = 1$. Under these circumstances, everyone improves with a treatment, while no one improves with control. A higher number needed to treat indicates more or less a treatment which is less effective.

Number needed to harm (NNH)

Definition 2.22 (Number needed to harm (NNH)).

$$NNH(A_t, B_t) \equiv \frac{1}{EER(A_t, B_t) - CER(A_t, B_t)} \quad (63)$$

The number needed to harm (Massel and Cruickshank, 2002), mathematically the inverse of the absolute risk increase, indicates at the end how many patients need to be exposed to a certain factor, in order to observe a harm in one patient that would not otherwise have been harmed.

Outcome prevalence rate (OPR)

Definition 2.23 (Outcome prevalence rate (OPR)).

$$OPR(A_t, B_t) \equiv \frac{p(a_t)}{p(B_t)} = \frac{a_t}{a_t + c_t} \quad (64)$$

Control prevalence rate (CPR)

Definition 2.24 (Control prevalence rate (CPR)).

$$CPR(A_t, B_t) \equiv \frac{p(b_t)}{p(B_t)} = \frac{b_t}{b_t + d_t} \quad (65)$$

Bias and confounding is present to some degree in all research. In order to assess the relationship of exposure with a disease or an outcome, a fictive control group (i.e. of newborn or of young children et cetera) can be of use too. Under certain circumstances, even a $CPR = 0$ is imaginable.

Absolute prevalence reduction (APR)

Definition 2.25 (Absolute prevalence reduction (APR)).

$$APR(A_t, B_t) \equiv CPR(A_t, B_t) - OPR(A_t, B_t) \quad (66)$$

Absolute prevalence increase (API)

Definition 2.26 (Absolute prevalence increase (API)).

$$API(A_t, B_t) \equiv OPR(A_t, B_t) - CPR(A_t, B_t) \quad (67)$$

Relative prevalence reduction (RPR)

Definition 2.27 (Relative prevalence reduction (RPR)).

$$\begin{aligned} RPR(A_t, B_t) &\equiv \frac{CPR(A_t, B_t) - OPR(A_t, B_t)}{CPR(A_t, B_t)} \\ &= 1 - RR(A_t, B_t)_{sc} \end{aligned} \quad (68)$$

The index NNS

Definition 2.28 (The index NNS).

$$NNS(A_t, B_t) \equiv \frac{1}{CPR(A_t, B_t) - OPR(A_t, B_t)} \quad (69)$$

Mathematically, the index NNS is the reciprocal of the absolute prevalence reduction.

The index NNI

Definition 2.29 (The index NNI).

$$NNI(A_t, B_t) \equiv \frac{1}{OPR(A_t, B_t) - CPR(A_t, B_t)} \quad (70)$$

Mathematically, the index NNI is the reciprocal of the absolute prevalence increase.

2.1.10. Odds ratio (OR)

Definition 2.30 (Odds ratio (OR)).

Odds ratios as an appropriate measure for estimating the relative risk have become widely used in medical reports of case-control studies. The odds ratio (Fisher, 1935, p. 50) is defined (Cox, 1958) as the ratio of the odds of an event occurring in one group with respect to the odds of its occurring in another group. Odds (Yule and Pearson, 1900, p. 273) ratio (OR) is a measure of association which quantifies the relationship between two binomial distributed random variables (exposure vs. outcome) and is related to Yule's (Yule and Pearson, 1900, p. 272) Q (Yule, 1912, p. 585/586). Two events A_t and B_t are regarded as independent if $(A_t, B_t) = 1$. Let

a_t = number of persons exposed to A_t and with disease B_t

b_t = number of persons exposed to A_t but without disease B_t

c_t = number of persons unexposed \underline{A}_t but with disease B_t

d_t = number of persons unexposed \underline{A}_t : and without disease B_t

$a_t + c_t$ = total number of persons with disease B_t (case-patients)

$b_t + d_t$ = total number of persons without disease B_t (controls).

Hereafter, consider the table 3. The odds' ratio (OR) is defined as

Table 3. The two by two table of random variables

		Conditioned/Outcome B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition/Exposure A_t	TRUE	a_t	b_t	A_t
	FALSE	c_t	d_t	\underline{A}_t
		B_t	\underline{B}_t	N_t

$$\begin{aligned}
 OR(A_t, B_t) &\equiv \left(\frac{a_t}{b_t} \right) / \left(\frac{c_t}{d_t} \right) \\
 &\equiv \left(\frac{a_t \times d_t}{b_t \times c_t} \right)
 \end{aligned} \tag{71}$$

Remark 2.1. Odds ratios can support logical fallacies and cause difficulties in drawing logically consistent conclusions. The chorus of voices is growing, which demand the immediate ending (Knol, 2012, Sackett, DL and Deeks, JJ and Altman, DG, 1996) of any use of Odds ratio.

Under conditions where $(b = 0)$, the measure of association odds ratio will collapse, because we need to divide by zero, as can be seen at eq. 71. However, according to today's rules of mathematics, a

division by zero is neither allowed nor generally accepted as possible. It does no harm to remind ourselves that in the case $b = 0$ the event A_t is a sufficient condition of B_t . In other words, odds ratio is not able to recognize elementary relationships of objective reality. In fact, it would be a failure not to recognize how dangerous and less valuable odds ratio is.

Under conditions where ($c = 0$) odds ratio collapses too, because we need again to divide by zero, as can be seen at eq. 71. However, and again, today's rules of mathematics don't allow us a division by zero. In point of fact, in the case $c = 0$ it is more than necessary to point out that A_t is a necessary condition of B_t . In other words, odds ratio or the cross-product ratio is not able to recognize elementary relationships of nature like necessary conditions. We can and need to overcome all the epistemological obstacles as backed by odds ratio entirety. Sooner rather than later, we should give up this measure of relationship completely.

2.1.11. Study design and bias

Systematic observation and experimentation, inductive and deductive reasoning are essential for any formation and testing of hypotheses and theories about the natural world. In one way or another, logically and mathematically sound scientific methods and concepts are crucial constituents of any scientific progress. When all goes well, different scientists at different times and places using the same scientific methodology should be able to generate the same scientific knowledge. However, more than half (52%) of scientists surveyed believe that studies do not successfully reproduce sufficiently similar or the same results as the original studies (Baker, 2016). In a very large study on publication bias in meta-analyses, Kicinski et al. (Kicinski et al., 2015) found evidence of publication bias even in systematic reviews. Therefore, a careful re-evaluation of the study/experimental design, the statistical methods and other scientific means which underpin scientific inquiry and research goals appears to be necessary once and again. While it is important to recognize the shortcoming of today's science, one issue which has shaped debates over studies published is the question: **has a study really measured what it set out to?** Even if studies carried out can vary greatly in detail, the data from the studies itself provide information about the credibility of the data.

Index of unfairness (IOU)

Definition 2.31 (Index of unfairness).

The index of unfairness (Barukčić, 2019b) (IOU) is defined as

$$p(\text{IOU}(A, B)) \equiv \text{Absolute} \left(\left(\frac{A+B}{N} \right) - 1 \right) \quad (72)$$

A very good study design should assure as much as possible a $p(\text{IOU}) = 0$. In point of fact, against the background of lacking enough experience with the use of $p(\text{IOU})$, a $p(\text{IOU})$ up to 0.25 could be of use too. An index of unfairness is of use to prove whether sample data are biased and whether sample data can be used for Chi-square based analysis of necessary conditions, of sufficient conditions and of causal relationships.

Index of independence (IOI)

Definition 2.32 (Index of independence).

The index of independence (Barukčić, 2019a) (IOI) is defined as

$$p(\text{IOI}(A_t, \underline{B}_t)) \equiv \text{Absolute} \left(\left(\frac{A_t + \underline{B}_t}{N} \right) - 1 \right) \quad (73)$$

or as

$$p(\text{IOI}(\underline{A}_t, B_t)) \equiv \text{Absolute} \left(\left(\frac{\underline{A}_t + B_t}{N} \right) - 1 \right) \quad (74)$$

A very good study design which aims to prove **an exclusion relationship or a causal relationship** should assure as much as possible a $p(\text{IOI}) = 0$. However, once again, against the background of lacking enough experience with the use of $p(\text{IOI})$, sample data with a $p(\text{IOI})$ up to 0.25 are of use too. Today, most double-blind placebo-controlled studies are based on the demand that $\mathbf{p}(\text{IOU}) = \mathbf{p}(\text{IOI})$ while the value of $p(\text{IOU})$ of has been widely neglected. Such an approach leads to unnecessary big sample sizes, the increase of cost, the waste of time and, most importantly of all, to epistemological systematically biased sample data and conclusions drawn. A change is necessary.

Index of relationship (IOR)

Definition 2.33 (Index of relationship (IOR)).

Due to several reasons, it is not always easy to identify the unique characteristics between two events like A_t and B_t . And more than that, it is difficult to decide what to do, and much more difficult to know in which direction one should think and which decision is right. Sometimes it is helpful to know at least something about the direction of the relationship between two events like A_t and B_t . Under conditions where $p(a_t) = p(A_t \wedge B_t)$, the index of relationship (Barukčić, 2021b), abbreviated as IOR, is defined as

$$\begin{aligned} \text{IOR}(A_t, B_t) &\equiv \left(\frac{p(A_t \wedge B_t)}{p(B_t) \times p(A_t)} \right) - 1 \\ &\equiv \left(\frac{p(a_t)}{p(B_t) \times p(A_t)} \right) - 1 \\ &\equiv \left(\left(\frac{N \times N \times p(a_t)}{N \times p(B_t) \times N \times p(A_t)} \right) - 1 \right) \\ &\equiv \left(\left(\frac{N \times a}{A \times B} \right) - 1 \right) \end{aligned} \quad (75)$$

where $p(A_t)$ denotes the probability of an event A_t at the Bernoulli trial t and $p(B_t)$ denotes the probability of another event B_t at the same Bernoulli trial t while $p(a_t)$ denotes the joint probability of $p(A_t \text{ AND } B_t)$ at the same Bernoulli trial t and a , A and B may denote the expectation values.

2.2. Conditions

2.2.1. Exclusion relationship

Definition 2.34 (Exclusion relationship [EXCL]).

Mathematically, the exclusion (EXCL) relationship, denoted by $p(A_t | B_t)$ in terms of statistics and probability theory, is defined (Barukčić, 1989, p. 68-70) as

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(A_t | B_t) &\equiv p(A_t \uparrow B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(b_t) + p(c_t) + p(d_t) \\
 &\equiv \frac{N \times (p(b_t) + p(c_t) + p(d_t))}{N} \\
 &\equiv \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N (\underline{A}_t \vee \underline{B}_t)}{N} \equiv \frac{b + c + d}{N} \\
 &\equiv \frac{b + \underline{A}}{N} \\
 &\equiv \frac{c + \underline{B}}{N} \\
 &\equiv +1
 \end{aligned} \tag{76}$$

Based on the 1913 Henry Maurice Sheffer (1882-1964) relationship, the Sheffer stroke (Nicod, 1917, Sheffer, 1913) usually denoted by \uparrow , it is $p(A_t \wedge B_t) \equiv 1 - p(A_t | B_t)$ (see table 4).

Table 4. A_t excludes B_t and vice versa.

		Conditioned (COVID-19) B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition (Vaccine)	TRUE	+0	$p(b_t)$	$p(\underline{A}_t)$
	FALSE	$p(c_t)$	$p(d_t)$	$p(\underline{A}_t)$
		$p(\underline{B}_t)$	$p(\underline{B}_t)$	+1

Example 2.1. Pfizer Inc. and BioNTech SE announced on Monday, November 09, 2020 - 06:45am results from a Phase 3 COVID-19 vaccine trial with 43,538 participants which provides evidence that their vaccine (BNT162b2) is preventing COVID-19 in participants without evidence of prior SARS-CoV-2 infection. In toto, 170 confirmed cases of COVID-19 were evaluated, with 8 in the vaccine group versus 162 in the placebo group. The exclusion relationship can be calculated as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(\text{Vaccine : BNT162b2} | \text{COVID} - 19(\text{infection})) &\equiv p(b_t) + p(c_t) + p(d_t) \\
 &\equiv 1 - p(a_t) \\
 &\equiv 1 - \left(\frac{8}{43538} \right) \\
 &\equiv +0,99981625
 \end{aligned} \tag{77}$$

with a P Value = 0,000184.

Following Kolmogorov's definition of an n-dimensional probability density (see also [Kolmogorov, Andreĭ Nikolaevich, 1950](#), p. 26) of random variables A_t, B_t et cetera at the point t , we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(A_t | B_t) &\equiv p(\underline{U}_t \cup \underline{W}_t) \\
 &\equiv 1 - p(A_t \cap B_t) \\
 &\equiv 1 - \int_{-\infty}^{A_t} \int_{-\infty}^{B_t} f(A_t, B_t) dA_t dB_t \\
 &\equiv +1
 \end{aligned} \tag{78}$$

while $p(A_t | B_t)$ would denote the cumulative distribution function of random variables and $f(A_t, B_t)$ is the joint density function.

2.2.2. Observational study and exclusion relationship

Under conditions of an observational study, the exclusion relationship follows approximately (see [Barukčić, 2021a](#)) as

$$p(A_t | B_t) \equiv p(A_t \uparrow B_t) \geq 1 - \frac{p(a_t)}{p(B_t)} \tag{79}$$

2.2.3. Experimental study and exclusion relationship

Under conditions of an experimental study, the exclusion relationship follows approximately (see [Barukčić, 2021a](#)) as

$$p(A_t | B_t) \equiv p(A_t \uparrow B_t) \geq 1 - \frac{p(a_t)}{p(A_t)} \tag{80}$$

2.2.4. The goodness of fit test of an exclusion relationship

Definition 2.35 (The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of an exclusion relationship).

Under some well known circumstances, testing hypothesis about an exclusion relationship $p(A_t | B_t)$ is possible by the chi-square distribution (also chi-squared or $\tilde{\chi}^2$ -distribution) too. The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of an exclusion relationship with degree of freedom (d. f.) of d. f. = 1 is calculated as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}((A_t | B_t) | A) &\equiv \frac{(b - (a + b))^2}{A} + \\
 &\quad \frac{((c + d) - A)^2}{A} \\
 &\equiv \frac{a^2}{A} + 0 \\
 &\equiv \frac{a^2}{A}
 \end{aligned} \tag{81}$$

or equally as

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}((A_t | B_t) | B) &\equiv \frac{(c - (a + c))^2}{B} + \\ &\quad \frac{((b + d) - \underline{B})^2}{B} \\ &\equiv \frac{a^2}{B} + 0 \\ &\equiv \frac{a^2}{B}\end{aligned}\tag{82}$$

and can be compared with a theoretical chi-square value at a certain level of significance α . The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ -distribution equals zero when the observed values are equal to the expected/theoretical values of an exclusion relationship/distribution $p(A_t | B_t)$, in which case the null hypothesis has to be accepted. Yate's (Yates, 1934) continuity correction was not used under these circumstances.

2.2.5. The left-tailed p Value of an exclusion relationship

Definition 2.36 (The left-tailed p Value of an exclusion relationship).

It is known that as a sample size, N , increases, a sampling distribution of a special test statistic approaches the normal distribution (central limit theorem). Under these circumstances, the left-tailed (lt) p Value (Barukčić, 2019c) of an exclusion relationship can be calculated as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}pValue_{lt}(A_t | B_t) &\equiv 1 - e^{-(1-p(A_t|B_t))} \\ &\equiv 1 - e^{-(a/N)}\end{aligned}\tag{83}$$

A low p-value may provide some evidence of statistical significance.

2.2.6. Neither nor conditions

Definition 2.37 (Neither A_t nor B_t conditions [NOR]).

Mathematically, a neither A_t nor B_t condition (or rejection according to the French philosopher and logician Jean George Pierre Nicod (1893-1924), i.e. Jean Nicod's statement (Nicod, 1924)) relationship (NOR), denoted by $p(A_t \downarrow B_t)$ in terms of statistics and probability theory, is defined (Barukčić, 1989, p. 68-70) as

$$\begin{aligned}p(A_t \downarrow B_t) &\equiv p(d_t) \\ &\equiv \frac{N - \sum_{t=1}^N (A_t \vee B_t)}{N} \equiv \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N (\underline{A}_t \wedge \underline{B}_t)}{N} \equiv \frac{N \times (p(d_t))}{N} \\ &\equiv \frac{d}{N} \\ &\equiv +1\end{aligned}\tag{84}$$

2.2.7. The Chi square goodness of fit test of a neither nor condition relationship

Definition 2.38 (The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a neither A_t nor B_t condition relationship).

A neither A_t nor B_t condition relationship $p(A_t \downarrow B_t)$ can be tested by the chi-square distribution (also chi-squared or $\tilde{\chi}^2$ -distribution). The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a neither A_t nor B_t condition relationship with degree of freedom (d. f.) of d. f. = 1 may be calculated as

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}((A_t \downarrow B_t) | A) &\equiv \frac{(d - (c + d))^2}{A} + \frac{((a + b) - A)^2}{A} \\ &\equiv \frac{c^2}{A} + 0\end{aligned}\quad (85)$$

or equally as

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}((A_t \downarrow B_t) | B) &\equiv \frac{(d - (b + d))^2}{B} + \frac{((a + c) - B)^2}{B} \\ &\equiv \frac{b^2}{B} + 0\end{aligned}\quad (86)$$

Yate's (Yates, 1934) continuity correction has not been used in this context.

2.2.8. The left-tailed p Value of a neither nor B condition relationship

Definition 2.39 (The left-tailed p Value of a neither A_t nor B_t condition relationship).

The left-tailed (lt) p Value (Barukčić, 2019c) of a neither A_t nor B_t condition relationship can be calculated as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}pValue_{lt}(A_t \downarrow B_t) &\equiv 1 - e^{-(1-p(A_t \downarrow B_t))} \\ &\equiv 1 - e^{-p(A_t \vee B_t)} \\ &\equiv 1 - e^{-((a+b+c)/N)}\end{aligned}\quad (87)$$

where \vee may denote disjunction or logical inclusive or. In this context, a low p-value indicates again a statistical significance. In general, it is $p(A_t \vee B_t) \equiv 1 - p(A_t \downarrow B_t)$ (see table 5).

Table 5. Neither A_t nor B_t relationship.

		Conditioned B_t		
		YES	NO	
Condition A_t	YES	0	0	0
	NO	0	1	1
		0	1	1

2.2.9. Necessary condition

Definition 2.40 (Necessary condition [*Conditio sine qua non*]).

Despite the most extended efforts, the current state of research on conditions and conditioned is still incomplete and very contradictory. However, even thousands of years ago and independently of any human mind and consciousness, water has been and is still a necessary condition for (human) life. Without water, there has been and there is no (human) life. It comes therefore as no surprise that one of the first documented attempts to present a rigorous theory of conditions and causation (see also [Aristotle et al., 1908](#), *Metaphysica* III 2 997a 10 and 13/14) came from the Greek philosopher and scientist Aristotle (384-322 BCE). Thus far, it is amazing that Aristotle himself made already a strict distinction between conditions and causes. Taking Aristotle very seriously, it is necessary to consider that

“... everything which has a potency in question has the potency ... of acting ...
not in all circumstances but on certain conditions ... ”

(see also [Aristotle et al., 1908](#), *Metaphysica* IX 5 1048a 14-19)

Before going into details, Aristotle went on to define the necessary condition as follows.

“... necessary ... means ...

without ... a condition, a thing cannot live ... ”

(see also [Aristotle et al., 1908](#), *Metaphysica* V 2 1015a 20-22)

In point of fact, Aristotle developed a theory of conditions and causality commonly referred to as the doctrine of four causes. Many aspects and general features of Aristotle’s logical concept of causality are meanwhile extensively and critically debated in secondary literature. However, even if the Greek philosophers Heraclitus, Plato, Aristotle et cetera numbers among the greatest philosophers of all time, the philosophy has evolved. Scientific knowledge and objective reality are deeply interrelated and cannot be reduced only to Greek philosophers like Aristotle. As mentioned at the start of the article, the specification of necessary conditions has traditionally been part of the philosopher’s investigations of different phenomena. Behind the need of a detailed evidence, it is justified to consider that philosophy

or philosophers as such certainly do not possess **a monopoly on the truth** and other areas such as medicine as well as other sciences and technology may transmit truths as well and may be of help to move beyond one's self enclosed unit. Seemingly, **the law's concept of causation** justifies to say few words on this subject, to put some light on some questions. Are there any criteria in law for deciding whether one action or an event A_t has caused another (generally harmful) event B_t ? What are these criteria? May causation in legal contexts differ from causation outside the law, for example, in science or in our everyday life and to what extent? Under which circumstances is it justified to tolerate such differences as may be found to exist? To understand just what is the law's concept of causation, it is useful to know how the highest court of states is dealing with causation. In the case *Hayes v. Michigan Central R. Co.*, 111 U.S. 228, the U.S. Supreme Court defined 1884 *conditio sine qua non* as follows: "... **causa sine qua non – a cause which, if it had not existed, the injury would not have taken place**". (Justice Matthews, Mr., 1884) The German Bundesgerichtshof für Strafsachen stressed once again the importance of *conditio sine qua non* relationship in his decision by defining the following: "**Ursache eines strafrechtlich bedeutsamen Erfolges jede Bedingung, die nicht hinweggedacht werden kann, ohne daß der Erfolg entfiel**" (Bundesgerichtshof für Strafsachen, 1951) Another lawyer elaborated on the basic issue of **identity and difference between cause and condition**. Von Bar was writing: "Die erste Voraussetzung, welche erforderlich ist, damit eine Erscheinung als die Ursache einer anderen bezeichnet werden könne, ist, daß jene eine der Bedingungen dieser sein. Würde die zweite Erscheinung auch dann eingetreten sein, wenn die erste nicht vorhanden war, so ist sie in keinem Falle Bedingung und noch weniger Ursache. Wo immer ein Kausalzusammenhang behauptet wird, da muß er wenigstens diese Probe aushalten ... **Jede Ursache ist notwendig auch eine Bedingung eines Ereignisses; aber nicht jede Bedingung ist Ursache zu nennen**." (Bar, 1871) Von Bar's position translated into English: *The first requirement, which is required, thus that something could be called as the cause of another, is that the one has to be one of the conditions of the other. If the second something had occurred even if the first one did not exist, so it is by no means a condition and still less a cause. Wherever a causal relationship is claimed, the same must at least withstand this test. . . Every cause is necessarily also a condition of an event too; but not every condition is cause too.* Thus far, let us consider among other the following in order to specify necessary conditions from another, probabilistic point of view. An event (i.e. A_t) which is a necessary condition of another event or outcome (i.e. B_t) must be given, must be present for a conditioned, for an event or for an outcome B_t to occur. A necessary condition (i.e. A_t) is a requirement which must be fulfilled **at every single Bernoulli trial t**, in order for a conditioned or an outcome (i.e. B_t) to occur, but it alone does not determine the occurrence of an event. In other words, if a necessary condition (i.e. A_t) is given, an outcome (i.e. B_t) need not occur. In contrast to a necessary condition, a 'sufficient' condition is the one condition which 'guarantees' that an outcome will take place or must occur for sure. Under which conditions we may infer about the unobserved and whether observations made are able at all to justify predictions about potential observations which have not yet been made or even general claims which may go even beyond the observed (*the 'problem of induction'*) is not the issue of the discussion at this point. Besides of the principal necessity of meeting such a challenge, a necessary condition of an event can but need not be at the same Bernoulli trial t a sufficient condition for an event to occur. However, theoretically, it is possible that an event or an outcome is determined by many necessary conditions. Let us focus to some extent on what this means, or in other words how much importance can we attribute to such a special case. *Example*. A human being cannot live without oxygen. A human being

cannot live without water. A human being cannot live without a brain. A human being cannot live without kidneys. A human being cannot live without ... et cetera. Thus far, even if oxygen is given, if water is given, if a brain is given, without functioning kidney's (or something similar) a human being will not survive on the long run. This example is of use to reach the following conclusion. Although it might seem somewhat paradoxical at first sight, **even under circumstances where a condition or an outcome depends on several different necessary conditions it is particularly important that every single of these necessary conditions for itself must be given otherwise the conditioned (i.e. the outcome) will not occur.** Mathematically, the necessary condition (SINE) relationship, denoted by $p(A_t \leftarrow B_t)$ in terms of statistics and probability theory, is defined (Barukčić, 1989, p. 15-28) as

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(A_t \leftarrow B_t) &\equiv p(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t) \equiv \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N (A_t \vee \underline{B}_t)}{N} \equiv \frac{(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t) \times p(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t)}{(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t)} \\
 &\equiv p(a_t) + p(b_t) + p(d_t) \\
 &\equiv \frac{N \times (p(a_t) + p(b_t) + p(d_t))}{N} \equiv \frac{E(A_t \leftarrow B_t)}{N} \\
 &\equiv \frac{a + b + d}{N} \equiv \frac{E(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t)}{N} \tag{88} \\
 &\equiv \frac{A + d}{N} \equiv \frac{E(A_t \leftarrow B_t)}{N} \\
 &\equiv \frac{a + \underline{B}}{N} \equiv \frac{E(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t)}{N} \\
 &\equiv +1
 \end{aligned}$$

where $E(A_t \leftarrow B_t) \equiv E(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t)$ indicates the expectation value of the necessary condition. In general, it is $p(A_t \prec B_t) \equiv 1 - p(A_t \leftarrow B_t)$ (see Table 6).

Table 6. Necessary condition.

		Conditioned B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition	TRUE	$p(a_t)$	$p(b_t)$	$p(A_t)$
	FALSE	+0	$p(d_t)$	$p(\underline{A}_t)$
		$p(\underline{B}_t)$	$p(\underline{B}_t)$	+1

Remark 2.2. A necessary condition A_t is characterized itself by the property that another event B_t will not occur if A_t is not given, if A_t did not occur (Barukčić, 1989, 1997, 2005, 2016b, 2017b,c, 2020a,b,c,d, Barukčić and Ufuoma, 2020). **Example.** Once again, a human being cannot live without water. A human being cannot live without gaseous oxygen, et cetera. Water itself is a necessary condition for human life. However, gaseous oxygen is a necessary condition for human life too. Thus far, even if water is given and even if water is a necessary condition for human life, without gaseous oxygen there will be no human life. In general, if a conditioned or an outcome B_t depends on the necessary condition A_t and equally on numerous other necessary conditions, an event B_t will not occur if A_t itself is not given independently of the occurrence of other necessary conditions.

Taking into account Kolmogorov's definition of an n-dimensional probability density (see also [Kolmogorov, Andreĭ Nikolaevich, 1950](#), p. 26) of random variables A_t , B_t et cetera at the (period of) time t , we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(A_t \leftarrow B_t) &\equiv +1 \\
 &\equiv +1 - p(c_t) \\
 &\equiv +1 - p(\underline{A}_t \cap B_t) \\
 &\equiv \left(\int_{-\infty}^{A_t} \int_{-\infty}^{B_t} f(A_t, B_t) dA_t dB_t \right) + \left(1 - \int_{-\infty}^{B_t} f(B_t) dB_t \right)
 \end{aligned} \tag{89}$$

while $p(A_t \leftarrow B_t)$ would denote the cumulative distribution function of random variables of a necessary condition. Another adequate formulation of a necessary condition is possible too.

2.2.10. The Chi-square goodness of fit test of a necessary condition relationship

Definition 2.41 (The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a necessary condition relationship).

Under some well known circumstances, hypothesis about the conditio sine qua non relationship $p(A_t \leftarrow B_t)$ can be tested by the chi-square distribution (also chi-squared or χ^2 -distribution), first described by the German statistician Friedrich Robert Helmert ([Helmert, 1876](#)) and later rediscovered by Karl Pearson ([Pearson, 1900](#)) in the context of a goodness of fit test. The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a conditio sine qua non relationship with degree of freedom (d. f.) of d. f. = 1 is calculated as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \leftarrow B_t | B) &\equiv \frac{(a - (a + c))^2}{B} + \\
 &\quad \frac{((b + d) - B)^2}{B} \\
 &\equiv \frac{c^2}{B} + 0 \\
 &\equiv \frac{c^2}{B}
 \end{aligned} \tag{90}$$

or equally as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \leftarrow B_t | A) &\equiv \frac{(d - (c + d))^2}{A} + \\
 &\quad \frac{((a + b) - A)^2}{A} \\
 &\equiv \frac{c^2}{A} + 0 \\
 &\equiv \frac{c^2}{A}
 \end{aligned} \tag{91}$$

and can be compared with a theoretical chi-square value at a certain level of significance α . It has not yet been finally clarified whether the use of Yate's (Yates, 1934) continuity correction is necessary at all.

2.2.11. The left-tailed p Value of the conditio sine qua non relationship

Definition 2.42 (The left-tailed p Value of the conditio sine qua non relationship).

The left-tailed (lt) p Value (Barukčić, 2019c) of the conditio sine qua non relationship can be calculated as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} pValue_{lt}(A_t \leftarrow B_t) &\equiv 1 - e^{-(1-p(A_t \leftarrow B_t))} \\ &\equiv 1 - e^{-(c/N)} \end{aligned} \quad (92)$$

2.2.12. Sufficient condition

Definition 2.43 (Sufficient condition [Conditio per quam]).

Mathematically, the sufficient condition (IMP) relationship, denoted by $p(A_t \rightarrow B_t)$ in terms of statistics and probability theory, is defined (Barukčić, 1989, p. 68-70) as

$$\begin{aligned} p(A_t \rightarrow B_t) &\equiv p(\underline{A}_t \vee B_t) \equiv \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N (\underline{A}_t \vee B_t)}{N} \equiv \frac{(\underline{A}_t \vee B_t) \times p(\underline{A}_t \vee B_t)}{(\underline{A}_t \vee B_t)} \\ &\equiv p(a_t) + p(c_t) + p(d_t) \\ &\equiv \frac{N \times (p(a_t) + p(c_t) + p(d_t))}{N} \\ &\equiv \frac{a + c + d}{N} \equiv \frac{E(\underline{A}_t \vee B_t)}{N} \\ &\equiv \frac{B + d}{N} \equiv \frac{E(A_t \rightarrow B_t)}{N} \\ &\equiv \frac{a + \underline{A}}{N} \\ &\equiv +1 \end{aligned} \quad (93)$$

It is $p(A_t \succ B_t) \equiv 1 - p(A_t \rightarrow B_t)$ (see Table 7).

Remark 2.3. A sufficient condition A_t is characterized by the property that another event B_t will occur if A_t is given, if A_t itself occurred (Barukčić, 1989, 1997, 2005, 2016b, 2017b,c, 2020a,b,c,d, Barukčić and Ufuoma, 2020). **Example.** The ground, the streets, the trees, human beings and many other objects too will become wet during heavy rain. Especially, **if** it is raining (event A_t), **then** human beings will become wet (event B_t). However, even if this is a common human wisdom, a human being equipped with an appropriate umbrella (denoted by R_t) need not become wet even during heavy rain. An appropriate

Table 7. Sufficient condition.

		Conditioned B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition	TRUE	$p(a_t)$	+0	$p(A_t)$
	FALSE	$p(c_t)$	$p(d_t)$	$p(\underline{A}_t)$
		$p(B_t)$	$p(\underline{B}_t)$	+1

umbrella (R_t) is similar to an event with the potential to counteract the occurrence of another event (B_t) and can be understood something as an **anti-dot** of another event. In other words, an appropriate umbrella is an antidote of the effect of rain on human body, an appropriate umbrella has the potential to protect humans from the effect of rain on their body. It is a good rule of thumb that the following relationship

$$p(A_t \rightarrow B_t) + p(R_t \wedge B_t) \equiv +1 \quad (94)$$

indicates that R_t is an antidote of A_t . However, taking a shower, swimming in a lake et cetera may make human hair wet too. More than anything else, however, these events does not affect the final outcome, the effect of raining on human body.

2.2.13. The Chi square goodness of fit test of a sufficient condition relationship

Definition 2.44 (The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a sufficient condition relationship).

Under some well known circumstances, testing hypothesis about the conditio per quam relationship $p(A_t \rightarrow B_t)$ is possible by the chi-square distribution (also chi-squared or $\tilde{\chi}^2$ -distribution) too. The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a conditio per quam relationship with degree of freedom (d. f.) of d. f. = 1 is calculated as

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \rightarrow B_t | A) &\equiv \frac{(a - (a+b))^2}{A} + \frac{((c+d) - \underline{A})^2}{\underline{A}} \\ &\equiv \frac{b^2}{A} + 0 \\ &\equiv \frac{b^2}{A} \end{aligned} \quad (95)$$

or equally as

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \rightarrow B_t | \underline{B}) &\equiv \frac{(d - (b + d))^2}{\underline{B}} + \\ &\quad \frac{((a + c) - B)^2}{B} \\ &\equiv \frac{b^2}{\underline{B}} + 0 \\ &\equiv \frac{b^2}{\underline{B}}\end{aligned}\tag{96}$$

and can be compared with a theoretical chi-square value at a certain level of significance α . The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ -distribution equals zero when the observed values are equal to the expected/theoretical values of the conditio per quam relationship/distribution $p(A_t \rightarrow B_t)$, in which case the null hypothesis is accepted. Yate's (Yates, 1934) continuity correction has not been used in this context.

2.2.14. The left-tailed p Value of the conditio per quam relationship

Definition 2.45 (The left-tailed p Value of the conditio per quam relationship).

The left-tailed (lt) p Value (Barukčić, 2019c) of the conditio per quam relationship can be calculated as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}pValue_{lt}(A_t \rightarrow B_t) &\equiv 1 - e^{-(1-p(A_t \rightarrow B_t))} \\ &\equiv 1 - e^{-(b/N)}\end{aligned}\tag{97}$$

Again, a low p-value indicates a statistical significance.

2.2.15. Necessary and sufficient conditions

Definition 2.46 (Necessary and sufficient conditions [EQV]).

The necessary and sufficient condition (EQV) relationship, denoted by $p(A_t \leftrightarrow B_t)$ in terms of statistics and probability theory, is defined (Barukčić, 1989, p. 68-70) as

$$\begin{aligned}p(A_t \leftrightarrow B_t) &\equiv \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N ((A_t \vee \underline{B}_t) \wedge (\underline{A}_t \vee B_t))}{N} \\ &\equiv p(a_t) + p(d_t) \\ &\equiv \frac{N \times (p(a_t) + p(d_t))}{N} \\ &\equiv \frac{a + d}{N} \\ &\equiv +1\end{aligned}\tag{98}$$

2.2.16. The Chi square goodness of fit test of a necessary and sufficient condition relationship

Definition 2.47 (The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a necessary and sufficient condition relationship).

Even the necessary and sufficient condition relationship $p(A_t \leftrightarrow B_t)$ can be tested by the chi-square distribution (also chi-squared or $\tilde{\chi}^2$ -distribution) too. The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a necessary and sufficient condition relationship with degree of freedom (d. f.) of d. f. = 1 is calculated as

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \leftrightarrow B_t | A) &\equiv \frac{(a - (a+b))^2}{A} + \frac{d - ((c+d))^2}{\underline{A}} \\ &\equiv \frac{b^2}{A} + \frac{c^2}{\underline{A}}\end{aligned}\quad (99)$$

or equally as

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \leftrightarrow B_t | B) &\equiv \frac{(a - (a+c))^2}{B} + \frac{d - ((b+d))^2}{\underline{B}} \\ &\equiv \frac{c^2}{B} + \frac{b^2}{\underline{B}}\end{aligned}\quad (100)$$

The calculated $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a necessary and sufficient condition relationship can be compared with a theoretical chi-square value at a certain level of significance α . Under conditions where the observed values are equal to the expected/theoretical values of a necessary and sufficient condition relationship/distribution $p(A_t \leftrightarrow B_t)$, the $\tilde{\chi}^2$ -distribution equals zero. It is to be cleared whether Yate's (Yates, 1934) continuity correction should be used at all.

2.2.17. The left-tailed p Value of a necessary and sufficient condition relationship

Definition 2.48 (The left-tailed p Value of a necessary and sufficient condition relationship).

The left-tailed (lt) p Value (Barukčić, 2019c) of a necessary and sufficient condition relationship can be calculated as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}pValue_{lt}(A_t \leftrightarrow B_t) &\equiv 1 - e^{-(1-p(A_t \leftrightarrow B_t))} \\ &\equiv 1 - e^{-((b+c)/N)}\end{aligned}\quad (101)$$

In this context, a low p-value indicates again a statistical significance. Table 8 may provide an overview of the theoretical distribution of a necessary and sufficient condition.

Table 8. Necessary and sufficient condition.

		Conditioned B_t		
		YES	NO	
Condition A_t	YES	1	0	1
	NO	0	1	1
		1	1	2

2.2.18. Either or conditions

Definition 2.49 (Either A_t or B_t conditions [NEQV]).

Mathematically, an either A_t or B_t condition relationship (NEQV), denoted by $p(A_t \succ\prec B_t)$ in terms of statistics and probability theory, is defined (Barukčić, 1989, p. 68-70) as

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(A_t \succ\prec B_t) &\equiv \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N ((A_t \wedge \underline{B}_t) \vee (\underline{A}_t \wedge B_t))}{N} \\
 &\equiv p(b_t) + p(c_t) \\
 &\equiv \frac{N \times (p(b_t) + p(c_t))}{N} \\
 &\equiv \frac{b + c}{N} \\
 &\equiv +1
 \end{aligned} \tag{102}$$

It is $p(A_t \succ\prec B_t) \equiv 1 - p(A_t \leftrightarrow B_t)$ (see Table 9).

Table 9. Either A_t or B_t relationship.

		Conditioned B_t		
		YES	NO	
Condition A_t	YES	0	1	1
	NO	1	0	1
		1	1	2

2.2.19. The Chi-square goodness of fit test of an either or condition relationship

Definition 2.50 (The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of an either or condition relationship).

An either or condition relationship $p(A_t \succ\prec B_t)$ can be tested by the chi-square distribution (also chi-squared or $\tilde{\chi}^2$ -distribution) too. The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of an either or condition relationship with degree of freedom (d. f.) of d. f. = 1 is calculated as

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}((A_t \succ \prec B_t) | A) &\equiv \frac{(b - (a + b))^2}{A} + \\ &\frac{c - ((c + d))^2}{\underline{A}} \\ &\equiv \frac{a^2}{A} + \frac{d^2}{\underline{A}}\end{aligned}\quad (103)$$

or equally as

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}((A_t \succ \prec B_t) | B) &\equiv \frac{(c - (a + c))^2}{B} + \\ &\frac{b - ((b + d))^2}{\underline{B}} \\ &\equiv \frac{a^2}{B} + \frac{d^2}{\underline{B}}\end{aligned}\quad (104)$$

Yate's (Yates, 1934) continuity correction has not been used in this context.

2.2.20. The left-tailed p Value of an either or condition relationship

Definition 2.51 (The left-tailed p Value of an either or condition relationship).

The left-tailed (lt) p Value (Barukčić, 2019c) of an either or condition relationship can be calculated as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}pValue_{lt}(A_t \succ \prec B_t) &\equiv 1 - e^{-(1 - p(A_t \succ \prec B_t))} \\ &\equiv 1 - e^{-((a+d)/N)}\end{aligned}\quad (105)$$

In this context, a low p-value indicates again a statistical significance.

2.2.21. Causal relationship k

The history of the denialism of causality in Philosophy, Mathematics, Statistics, Physics et cetera is very long. We only recall David Hume's (1711-1776) account of causation and his inappropriate reduction of the cause-effect relationship to a simple habitual connection in human thinking or Immanuel Kant's (1724-1804) initiated trial to consider causality as nothing more but a '*a priori*' given category (Langsam, 1994) in human reasoning and other similar attempts too. It is worth noting in this context that especially Karl Pearson (1857 - 1936) himself has been engaged in a long lasting and never-ending crusade against causation too. **"Pearson categorically denies the need for an independent concept of causal relation beyond correlation ... he exterminated causation from statistics before it had a chance to take root"** (Pearl, 2000) At the beginning of the 20th century notable proponents of **conditionalism** like the German anatomist and pathologist David Paul von Hansemann (Hansemann, David Paul von, 1912) (1858 - 1920) and the biologist and physiologist Max Richard Constantin Verworn (Verworn, 1912) (1863 - 1921) started a new attack (Kröber, 1961) on the principle of causality. In his essay "Kausale und konditionale Weltanschauung" Verworn (Verworn, 1912) presented "an exposition of 'conditionism' as contrasted with 'causalism,' (Unknown, 1913) while ignoring cause and effect relationships completely. **"Das Ding ist also identisch mit der Gesamtheit seiner Bedingungen."** (Verworn, 1912) However, Verworn's goal to exterminate causality completely out of science was hindered by the further development of research. The history of futile attempts to refute **the principle of causality** culminated in a publication by the German born physicist Werner Karl Heisenberg (1901 - 1976). Heisenberg put forward an illogical, inconsistent and confusing uncertainty principle which opened the door to wishful thinking and logical fallacies in physics and in science as such. Heisenberg's unjustified reasoning ended in an act of a manifestly unfounded conclusion: **"Weil alle Experimente den Gesetzen der Quantenmechanik und damit der Gleichung (1) unterworfen sind, so wird durch die Quantenmechanik die Ungültigkeit des Kausalgesetzes definitiv festgestellt."** (Heisenberg, Werner Karl, 1927) while 'Gleichung (1)' denotes Heisenberg's uncertainty principle. Einstein's himself, a major contributor to quantum theory and in the same respect a major critic of quantum theory, disliked Heisenberg's uncertainty principle fundamentally while Einstein's opponents used Heisenberg's Uncertainty Principle against Einstein. After the End of the German Nazi initiated Second World War with unimaginable brutality and high human losses and a death toll due to an industrially organised mass killing of people by the German Nazis which did not exist in this way before, Werner Heisenberg visited Einstein in Princeton (New Jersey, USA) in October 1954 (Neffe, 2006). Einstein agreed to meet Heisenberg only for a very short period of time but their encounter lasted longer. However, there were not only a number of differences between Einstein and Heisenberg, these two physicists did not really love each other. "Einstein remarked that the inventor of the uncertainty principle was a 'big Nazi'..." (Neffe, 2006) Albert Einstein (1879 - 1955) took again the opportunity to refuse to endorse **Heisenberg's uncertainty principle** as a fundamental law of nature and rightly too. Meanwhile, Heisenberg's uncertainty principle is refuted (see Barukčić, 2011a, 2014, 2016a) for several times but still not exterminated completely out of physics and out of science as such. In contrast to such extreme anti-causal positions as advocated by Heisenberg and the **Copenhagen interpretation of quantum mechanics**, the search for a (mathematical) solution of *the issue of causal inferences* is as old as human mankind itself ("*i. e. Aristotle's Doctrine of the Four Causes*") (Hennig, 2009) even if there is still little to go on. It is appropriate to specify especially the position of D'Holbach (Holbach, Paul Henri Thiry Baron de, 1770). D'Holbach (1723-1789) him-

self linked cause and effect or causality as such to changes. “**Une cause, est un être qui e met un autre en mouvement, ou qui produit quelque changement en lui. L’effet est le changement qu’un corps produit dans un autre ...**”(Holbach, Paul Henri Thiry Baron de, 1770) D’Holbach infers in the following: “**De l’action et de la réaction continue de tous les êtres que la nature renferme, il résulte une suite de causes et d’effets ..**”(Holbach, Paul Henri Thiry Baron de, 1770) With more or less meaningless or none progress on the matter in hand even in the best possible conditions, it is not surprising that authors are suggesting more and more different approaches and models for causal inference. Indeed, the hope is justified that logically consistent *statistical methods of causal inference* can help scientist to achieve so much with so little. One of the methods of causal inference in Bio-sciences are based on the known Henle(Henle, 1840) (1809–1885) - Koch(Koch, 1878) (1843–1910) postulates (Carter, 1985) which are applied especially for the identification of a causative agent of an (infectious) disease. However, the pathogenesis of most chronic diseases is more or less very complex and potentially involves the interaction of several factors. In practice, from the ‘pure culture’ requirement of the Henle-Koch postulates insurmountable difficulties may emerge. In light of subsequent developments (PCR methodology, immune antibodies et cetera) it is appropriate to review the full validity of the Henle-Koch postulates in our days. In 1965, Sir Austin Bradford Hill (Hill, 1965) published nine criteria (the ‘Bradford Hill Criteria ’) in order to determine whether observed epidemiologic associations are causal. Somewhat worrying, is at least the fact that, Hill’s “... fourth characteristic is *the temporal relationship of the association* ” and so-to-speak just a reformulation of the ‘*post hoc ergo propter hoc*’(Barukčić, 1989, Woods and Walton, 1977) logical fallacy through the back-door and much more then this. It is questionable whether association as such can be treated as being identical with causation. Unfortunately, due to several reasons, it seems therefore rather problematic to rely on Bradford Hill Criteria carelessly. Meanwhile, several other and competing mathematical or statistical approaches for causal inference have been discussed (Barukčić, 1989, 1997, 2005, 2016b, 2017a,c, Bohr, 1937, Dempster, 1990, Espejo, 2007, Hessen, Johannes, 1928, Hesslow, 1976, 1981, Korch, Helmut, 1965, Pearl, 2000, Schlick, Friedrich Albert Moritz, 1931, Suppes, 1970, Zesar, 2013) or even established (Barukčić, 1989, 1997, 2005, 2016b, 2017a,c). Nevertheless, the question is still not answered, is it at all possible to establish a cause effect relationship between two factors while applying only certain statistical (Sober, 2001) methods?

Definition 2.52 (Causal relationship k).

Nonetheless, mathematically, the causal(Barukčić, 2011a,b, 2012) relationship (Barukčić, 1989, 1997, 2005, 2016b, 2017a,c, 2021d) between a cause U_t (German: Ursache) and an effect W_t (German: Wirkung), denoted by $k(U_t, W_t)$, is defined at each single(Thompson, 2006) Bernoulli trial t in terms of statistics and probability theory as

$$\begin{aligned}
 k(U_t, W_t) &\equiv \frac{\sigma(U_t, W_t)}{\sigma(U_t) \times \sigma(W_t)} \\
 &\equiv \frac{p(U_t \wedge W_t) - p(U_t) \times p(W_t)}{\sqrt{(p(U_t) \times (1 - p(U_t))) \times (p(W_t) \times (1 - p(W_t)))}}
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{106}$$

where $\sigma(U_t, W_t)$ denotes the co-variance between a cause U_t and an effect W_t at every single Bernoulli trial t , $\sigma(U_t)$ denotes the standard deviation of a cause U_t at the same single Bernoulli trial t , $\sigma(W_t)$

denotes the standard deviation of an effect W_t at same single Bernoulli trial t . Table 10 illustrates the theoretically possible relationships between a cause and an effect.

Table 10. Sample space and the causal relationship k

		Effect B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Cause A_t	TRUE	$p(a_t)$	$p(b_t)$	$p(U_t)$
	FALSE	$p(c_t)$	$p(d_t)$	$p(\underline{U}_t)$
		$p(W_t)$	$p(\underline{W}_t)$	+1

However, even if one thinks to recognise the trace of Bravais (Bravais, 1846) (1811-1863) - Pearson's (1857-1936) "product-moment coefficient of correlation" (Galton, 1877, Pearson, 1896) inside the causal relationship k (Barukčić, 1989, 1997, 2005, 2016b, 2017a,c) both are completely different. According to Pearson: "The fundamental theorems of correlation were for the first time and almost exhaustively discussed by Bravais ('Analyse mathématique sur les probabilités des erreurs de situation d'un point.' *Memoires par divers Savans, T. IX., Paris, 1846, pp. 255-332*) nearly half a century ago." (Pearson, 1896) Neither does it make much sense to elaborate once again on the issue causation (Blalock, 1972) and correlation, since both are not identical (Sober, 2001) nor does it make sense to insist on the fact that "Pearson's philosophy discouraged him from looking too far behind phenomena." (Haldane, 1957) Whereas it is essential to consider that the causal relationship k , in contrast to Pearson's product-moment coefficient of correlation (Pearson, 1896) or to Pearson's phi coefficient (Pearson, 1904b), is defined at every single Bernoulli trial t . This might be a very small difference. However, even a small difference might determine a difference. However, in this context and in any case, this small difference makes (Barukčić, 2018a) the difference.

2.2.22. Cause and effect

Definition 2.53 (Cause and effect).

What is the cause, what is the effect? Under conditions of a **positive** causal relationship k , an event U_t which is for sure a cause of another event W_t is at the same time t a necessary and sufficient condition of an event W_t . Table 11 may illustrate this relationship.

Table 11. What is the cause, what is the effect?

		Effect W_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Cause U_t	TRUE	+1	+0	$p(U_t)$
	FALSE	+0	+1	$p(\underline{U}_t)$
		$p(W_t)$	$p(\underline{W}_t)$	+1

As can be seen, there is a kind of strange mirroring between U_t and W_t at the same Bernoulli trial t . Lastly, both are converses of each other too. In other words, U_t 's being a necessary condition of W_t 's is equivalent to W_t 's being a sufficient condition of U_t 's (and vice versa). In general, it is

$$(U_t \vee \underline{W}_t) \equiv (\underline{W}_t \vee U_t) \equiv ((U_t \vee \underline{W}_t) \wedge (\underline{W}_t \vee U_t)) \equiv +1 \quad (107)$$

In our everyday words,

without

U_t

no

W_t

is equivalent with

if

W_t

then

U_t

and vice versa.

Necessary and sufficient conditions are relationships used to describe the relationship between two events at the same Bernoulli trial t . In more detail, if U_t then W_t is equivalent with W_t is necessary for U_t , because the truth of U_t guarantees the truth of W_t . In general, it is

$$(\underline{U}_t \vee W_t) \equiv (W_t \vee \underline{U}_t) \equiv ((\underline{U}_t \vee W_t) \wedge (W_t \vee \underline{U}_t)) \equiv +1 \quad (108)$$

In other words, it is impossible to have U_t without W_t (Bloch, 2011). Similarly, U_t is sufficient for W_t , because U_t being true always implies that W_t is true, but U_t not being true does not always imply that W_t is not true.

For instance, **without** gaseous oxygen (U_t), there would be **no** burning wax candle (W_t); hence the relationship **if** burning wax candle (W_t) **then** gaseous oxygen (U_t) is equally true and given.

This simple example may illustrate the reason why a sufficient condition alone is not enough to describe a cause completely. The relationship **if** burning wax candle (W_t) **then** gaseous oxygen (U_t) is given. Independently of this fact, a burning wax candle is not the cause of gaseous oxygen. Therefore, in order to be a cause of oxygen, additional evidence is necessary that a burning wax candle is a necessary condition of gaseous oxygen too. However, even if the relationship **without** gaseous oxygen **no** burning wax candle is given, this relationship is not given vice versa. The relationship **without** burning wax candle **no** gaseous oxygen is not given. Like other fundamental concepts, the concepts of cause and effect can be associated with difficulties too. In order to recognise a causal relationship between U_t and W_t , it is necessary that the same study or that at least different studies provide evidence of a necessary condition between U_t and W_t and of a sufficient condition between U_t and W_t and if possible of a **necessary and sufficient condition** between U_t and W_t too.

Mathematically, a necessary and sufficient condition between U_t and W_t is defined as

$$(U_t \vee \underline{W}_t) \wedge (\underline{U}_t \vee W_t) \equiv +1 \quad (109)$$

However, I think it necessary to make a clear distinction between a necessary and sufficient condition and the converse relationship (Eq. 107) above.

$$((U_t \vee \underline{W}_t) \wedge (\underline{W}_t \vee U_t)) \neq (U_t \vee \underline{W}_t) \wedge (\underline{U}_t \vee W_t) \quad (110)$$

2.3. *Statistical methods*

The probability of the necessary (Barukčić, 2021d) condition $p(\text{SINE})$ has been calculated and tested for statistical significance. The probability of the sufficient (Barukčić, 2021d) condition $p(\text{IMP})$ has been calculated, the statistical significance of this relationship has been proofed. The chi-square goodness of fit test with one degree of freedom has been used to test whether the sample data published fit a certain theoretical distribution in the population. The causal relationship k (Barukčić, 2021d) has been calculated to evaluate a possible causal relationship between the events/factors analysed. The hypergeometric (Fisher, 1922, Gonin, 1936, Huygens and van Schooten, 1657, Pearson, 1899) distribution (HGD) has been used to test the one-sided significance of the causal relationship k . The study (design) bias has been controlled by IOI, the index of independence (Barukčić, 2019a) and IOU, the index of unfairness (Barukčić, 2019b). All the data were analysed using MS Excel (Microsoft Corporation, USA). The p values less than 0.05 were considered to indicate a statistically significant difference.

2.4. Axioms

2.4.1. Axiom I. Lex identitatis

In this context, we define axiom I as the expression

$$+ 1 = +1 \quad (111)$$

2.4.2. Axiom II. Lex contradictionis

In this context, axiom II or **lex contradictionis**, the negative of lex identitatis, or

$$+ 0 = +1 \quad (112)$$

and equally the most simple form of a contradiction formulated.

2.4.3. Axiom III. Lex negationis

$$\neg(0) \times 0 = 1 \quad (113)$$

where \neg denotes (logical (Boole, 1854) or natural) negation (Ayer, 1952, Förster and Melamed, 2012, Hedwig, 1980, Heinemann, Fritz H., 1943, Horn, 1989, Koch, 1999, Kunen, 1987, Newstadt, 2015, Royce, 1917, Speranza and Horn, 2010, Wedin, 1990). In this context, there is some evidence that $\neg(1) \times 1 = 0$. In other words, it is $(\neg(1) \times 1) \times (\neg(0) \times 0) = 1$

3. Results

3.1. Causal relationship and study design

Theorem 3.1 (Causal relationship and study design). *An essential key condition to ensure a comparability of the results of experimental and non-experimental studies which aim to investigate a cause-effect relationship between events is an index of independence of*

$$p(\text{IOI}(A_t, \underline{B}_t)) \equiv \text{Absolute} \left(\frac{A_t + \underline{B}_t}{N} - 1 \right) \equiv +0 \quad (114)$$

Proof by direct proof. The premise

$$+1 \equiv +1 \quad (115)$$

is true. Multiple definitions of causation have been offered in science. But despite much discussion about causation, it is clear that an effect cannot exist without a cause. In other words, without a cause (A_t), no effect (B_t). A necessary condition relationship between cause and effect is one determining part of a deterministic causal relationship, and appears to best fit the characteristics of a useful definition of causation. In the following, we rearrange the premise (see equation 88, p. 35) and do obtain

$$p(A_t \leftarrow B_t) \equiv +1 \quad (116)$$

Logically consistent definitions of deterministic causation need to consider, how to characterize a cause. Another aspect of deterministic causation is the need that a cause produces its own effect. In other words, if cause, then effect. In the following, we rearrange equation 116 and do obtain (see equation 93, p. 37)

$$p(A_t \leftarrow B_t) \equiv p(A_t \rightarrow B_t) \quad (117)$$

Equation 117 draws attention to the fact that a cause is a necessary and sufficient condition of an effect. Table 12 is providing an overview of this relationship.

Table 12. Necessary and sufficient condition and causal relationship

		Effect B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Cause A_t	TRUE	+1	+0	$p(A_t)$
	FALSE	+0	+1	$p(\underline{A}_t)$
		$p(B_t)$	$p(\underline{B}_t)$	+1

In case of a contra-valent relationship (either A_t or B_t), we expect the relationship,

$$1 - p(A_t \leftarrow B_t) \equiv 1 - p(A_t \rightarrow B_t) \quad (118)$$

which has no influence whatsoever on the progress of this investigation. Nevertheless, equation 117 changes (see equation 88, p. 35). It is

$$\frac{a_t + \underline{B}_t}{N} \equiv p(A_t \rightarrow B_t) \quad (119)$$

Equation 119 becomes (see equation 93, p. 37)

$$\frac{a_t + \underline{B}_t}{N} \equiv \frac{a_t + \underline{A}_t}{N} \quad (120)$$

Equation 120 simplifies as

$$a_t + \underline{B}_t \equiv a_t + \underline{A}_t \quad (121)$$

or as

$$\underline{B}_t \equiv \underline{A}_t \quad (122)$$

or as

$$N - \underline{B}_t \equiv N - \underline{A}_t \quad (123)$$

or as

$$\underline{B}_t \equiv \underline{A}_t \quad (124)$$

and as

$$\underline{B}_t \equiv N - \underline{A}_t \quad (125)$$

Rearranging equation 125 it is

$$\underline{A}_t + \underline{B}_t \equiv N \quad (126)$$

Equation 126 changes to

$$\frac{\underline{A}_t + \underline{B}_t}{N} \equiv +1 \quad (127)$$

and to

$$\frac{\underline{A}_t + \underline{B}_t}{N} - 1 \equiv +0 \quad (128)$$

The study design of a study which aims to investigate a cause-effect relationship (see equation 117) between events should ensure as much as possible an index of independence (Barukčić, 2019a) (IOI) as

$$IOI(A_t, \underline{B}_t) \equiv \frac{\underline{A}_t + \underline{B}_t}{N} - 1 \equiv +0 \quad (129)$$

Taking the absolute value from equation 129, we obtain the value of the index of independence (Barukčić, 2019a) (IOI) as

$$p(IOI(A_t, \underline{B}_t)) \equiv \text{Absolute} \left(\frac{\underline{A}_t + \underline{B}_t}{N} - 1 \right) \equiv +0 \quad (130)$$

□

This result is valid for a contra-valent relationship (either A_t or B_t) and an exclusion relationship (A_t excludes B_t and vice versa) too.

3.2. Independence of events

In order to characterize the relationship between cause and effect while using the tools of probability theory (i.e. probabilistic ¹⁶ causation), it is necessary to address at least one preliminary issue, the relationship between the law of independence and the relationship between cause and effect. The scientific concept of independence (Einstein, 1948, Kolmogoroff, Andreï Nikolaevich, 1933, Moivre, 1718) is of fundamental importance in (natural) sciences. Einstein himself puts it in a nutshell: “*Ohne die Annahme einer . . . Unabhängigkeit der . . . Dinge voneinander . . . wäre physikalisches Denken . . . nicht möglich.*” (Einstein, 1948). In general, a minimum requirement for any concept of causation is the possibility of a method to demonstrate the absence of independence at the same (period of) time Bernoulli trial t between events with certainty.

Theorem 3.2 (Independence of events). *In general, assuming independence of the events A_t and B_t , it holds that*

$$\frac{N \times a_t}{A_t} \equiv B_t \quad (131)$$

Proof by direct proof. In the case of independence of events, it is

$$p(A_t \wedge B_t) \equiv p(a_t) \equiv p(A_t) \times p(B_t) \quad (132)$$

Multiplying equation 132 by the sample size / population's size N^2 , while the probability of an event is constant from trial to trial, it is

$$N^2 \times p(a_t) \equiv N \times p(A_t) \times N \times p(B_t) \quad (133)$$

Simplifying equation 133, it is

$$N \times a_t \equiv A_t \times B_t \quad (134)$$

Equation 134 is rearranged as

$$\frac{N \times a_t}{A_t} \equiv B_t \quad (135)$$

□

3.3. Bias and index of independence

Random error or lack of precision and other factors while investigating a relationship between a cause (i.e. an exposure) and an effect cannot be excluded completely or absolutely and can cause false

¹⁶Parascandola M. Causes, risks, and probabilities: probabilistic concepts of causation in chronic disease epidemiology. *Prev Med.* 2011 Oct;53(4-5):232-4. doi: 10.1016/j.ypmed.2011.09.007. Epub 2011 Oct 5. PMID: 21983603.

conclusions and be potentially misleading. In general, bias ¹⁷, ¹⁸, ¹⁹, ²⁰ in research as determined by the deviation of data collection, data analysis, data interpretation, publication et cetera from the truth can occur either unintentionally or intentionally. It is necessary to undertake all known actions available to reduce or minimize bias as much as possible. In spite of that, or exactly because of that, the question arises whether bias can be induced by an index of independence. A study design which is based on an index of independence need to ensure to recognize an independence of events without any restriction.

Theorem 3.3 (Bias and index of independence). *A study design which is based on the index of independence enables the detection of independent events. In this case, it is for example*

$$p(A_t)^2 \equiv p(a_t) \quad (136)$$

Proof by direct proof. The premise

$$+ 1 \equiv +1 \quad (137)$$

is true. In the following, we rearrange the premise. We obtain

$$A_t \equiv A_t \quad (138)$$

The index of independence is based on the relationship $A_t \equiv B_t$ (see equation 124). Equation 138 becomes

$$A_t \equiv B_t \quad (139)$$

Equation 139 changes to (see equation 135)

$$A_t \equiv \frac{N \times a_t}{A_t} \quad (140)$$

Simplifying equation 140, we obtain

$$A_t \times A_t \equiv N \times a_t \quad (141)$$

Dividing equation 141 by N^2 , it is

$$\frac{A_t \times A_t}{N \times N} \equiv \frac{N \times a_t}{N \times N} \quad (142)$$

or

$$p(A_t)^2 \equiv p(a_t) \quad (143)$$

□

¹⁷Sackett DL. Bias in analytic research. *J Chronic Dis.* 1979;32(1-2):51-63. doi: 10.1016/0021-9681(79)90012-2. PMID: 447779.

¹⁸Delgado-Rodríguez M, Llorca J. Bias. *J Epidemiol Community Health.* 2004 Aug;58(8):635-41. doi: 10.1136/jech.2003.008466. PMID: 15252064; PMCID: PMC1732856.

¹⁹Simundić AM. Bias in research. *Biochem Med (Zagreb).* 2013;23(1):12-5. doi: 10.11613/bm.2013.003. PMID: 23457761; PMCID: PMC3900086.

²⁰Bradley SH, DeVito NJ, Lloyd KE, Richards GC, Rombey T, Wayant C, Gill PJ. Reducing bias and improving transparency in medical research: a critical overview of the problems, progress and suggested next steps. *J R Soc Med.* 2020 Nov;113(11):433-443. doi: 10.1177/0141076820956799. PMID: 33167771; PMCID: PMC7673265.

Theorem 3.4 (Relative risk and causal relationship k). *Under certain specific circumstances, the relative risk demands that the causal relationship k is given by the equation*

$$k(A_t, B_t) \equiv \frac{\left(p(A_t) \times RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc} \times \frac{p(c_t)}{p(NotA_t)} \right) - p(A_t) \times p(B_t)}{\sqrt[2]{(p(A_t) \times (1 - p(A_t))) \times (p(B_t) \times (1 - p(B_t)))}} \quad (144)$$

Proof by direct proof. The premise

$$+1 \equiv +1 \quad (145)$$

is true. In the following, we rearrange the premise. The relative (Cornfield, 1951, Sadowsky et al., 1953) risk (see Barukčić, 2021c) is denoted as $RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc}$. We obtain

$$RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc} \equiv RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc} \quad (146)$$

Equation 146 changes according to equation 54 to

$$\frac{\frac{p(a_t)}{p(A_t)}}{\frac{p(c_t)}{p(NotA_t)}} \equiv RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc} \quad (147)$$

and to

$$p(a_t) \equiv p(A_t) \times RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc} \times \frac{p(c_t)}{p(NotA_t)} \quad (148)$$

The causal relationship itself is defined (see equation 106) as

$$k(A_t, B_t) \equiv \frac{p(a_t) - p(A_t) \times p(B_t)}{\sqrt[2]{(p(A_t) \times (1 - p(A_t))) \times (p(B_t) \times (1 - p(B_t)))}} \quad (149)$$

We substitute the result of equation 148 into equation 149. There are circumstances where the relationship between the relative risk and the causal relationship k is given by the relationship

$$k(A_t, B_t) \equiv \frac{\left(p(A_t) \times RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc} \times \frac{p(c_t)}{p(NotA_t)} \right) - p(A_t) \times p(B_t)}{\sqrt[2]{(p(A_t) \times (1 - p(A_t))) \times (p(B_t) \times (1 - p(B_t)))}} \quad (150)$$

□

Theorem 3.5 (Odds ratio and causal relationship k). *Under specific circumstances, an odds ratio determines the causal relationship k by the equation*

$$k(A_t, B_t) \equiv \frac{\left(p(b_t) \times OR(A_t, B_t) \times \left(\frac{p(c_t)}{p(d_t)} \right) \right) - p(A_t) \times p(B_t)}{\sqrt[2]{(p(A_t) \times (1 - p(A_t))) \times (p(B_t) \times (1 - p(B_t)))}} \quad (151)$$

Proof by direct proof. The premise

$$+ 1 \equiv +1 \quad (152)$$

is true. In the following, we rearrange the premise. An odds ratio (Cox, 1958, Fisher, 1935, p. 50) as the ratio of the odds of an event occurring in one group with respect to the odds of its occurring in another group is denoted as $OR(A_t, B_t)$. We obtain

$$OR(A_t, B_t) \equiv OR(A_t, B_t) \quad (153)$$

Equation 153 becomes

$$\left(\frac{(a_t) \times (d_t)}{(b_t) \times (c_t)} \right) \equiv \left(\frac{N \times p(a_t) \times N \times p(d_t)}{N \times p(b_t) \times N \times p(c_t)} \right) \equiv \left(\frac{p(a_t)}{p(b_t)} \right) / \left(\frac{p(c_t)}{p(d_t)} \right) \equiv OR(A_t, B_t) \quad (154)$$

Equation 154 becomes

$$p(a_t) \equiv p(b_t) \times OR(A_t, B_t) \times \left(\frac{p(c_t)}{p(d_t)} \right) \quad (155)$$

The causal relationship itself is defined (see equation 106) as

$$k(A_t, B_t) \equiv \frac{p(a_t) - p(A_t) \times p(B_t)}{\sqrt[2]{(p(A_t) \times (1 - p(A_t))) \times (p(B_t) \times (1 - p(B_t)))}} \quad (156)$$

We substitute the result of equation 155 into equation 156. Under specific circumstances, an odds ratio defines the causal relationship k by the equation

$$k(A_t, B_t) \equiv \frac{\left(p(b_t) \times OR(A_t, B_t) \times \left(\frac{p(c_t)}{p(d_t)} \right) \right) - p(A_t) \times p(B_t)}{\sqrt[2]{(p(A_t) \times (1 - p(A_t))) \times (p(B_t) \times (1 - p(B_t)))}} \quad (157)$$

□

4. Discussion

Any study design²¹ with its very own strengths and weaknesses has the potential of clouding our view of the essential and to endanger among other the possibility to arrive at correct study conclusions. Therefore, several aspects of a study design^{22, 23, 24, 25} need to be addressed very carefully in the design phase of any study, otherwise problems and contradictions (see [Hegel, Georg Wilhelm Friedrich, 1812, 1813, 1816](#)) are pre-ordained. The selection of a study design need to incorporate consideration of several aspects, including sample size calculations, too. An appropriate selection of a study design is only one of the many elements in successful research. Sample size calculations are not of minor importance too. In general, a sample that is too large might induce a waste of time, money and harm people, while a sample size which is too small²⁶ might not be able to detect any effect. The design²⁷ of studies that seek to investigate cause-and-effect^{28, 29} relationships between events needs to be a lot more careful and should pay special attention to the requirement of an index of independence as much as possible near to zero or

$$p(IOI(A_t, B_t)) \equiv \text{Absolute} \left(\frac{A_t + B_t}{N} - 1 \right) \equiv +0 \quad (158)$$

²¹Thiese MS. Observational and interventional study design types; an overview. *Biochem Med (Zagreb)*. 2014;24(2):199-210. doi: 10.11613/BM.2014.022. Epub 2014 Jun 15. PMID: 24969913; PMCID: PMC4083571.

²²Elston DM. Study design and statistical analysis. *J Am Acad Dermatol*. 2018 Aug;79(2):207. doi: 10.1016/j.jaad.2017.11.004. Epub 2017 Nov 9. PMID: 29128448.

²³Parab S, Bhalerao S. Study designs. *Int J Ayurveda Res*. 2010 Apr;1(2):128-31. doi: 10.4103/0974-7788.64406. PMID: 20814529; PMCID: PMC2924977.

²⁴Kuehne F, Jahn B, Conrads-Frank A, Bundo M, Arvandi M, Endel F, Popper N, Endel G, Urach C, Gyimesi M, Murray EJ, Danaei G, Gaziano TA, Pandya A, Siebert U. Guidance for a causal comparative effectiveness analysis emulating a target trial based on big real world evidence: when to start statin treatment. *J Comp Eff Res*. 2019 Sep;8(12):1013-1025. doi: 10.2217/ce-2018-0103. Epub 2019 Sep 12. PMID: 31512926.

²⁵Dahabreh IJ, Haneuse SJA, Robins JM, Robertson SE, Buchanan AL, Stuart EA, Hernán MA. Study Designs for Extending Causal Inferences From a Randomized Trial to a Target Population. *Am J Epidemiol*. 2021 Aug 1;190(8):1632-1642. doi: 10.1093/aje/kwaa270. PMID: 33324969; PMCID: PMC8536837.

²⁶Noordzij M, Dekker FW, Zoccali C, Jager KJ. Sample size calculations. *Nephron Clin Pract*. 2011;118(4):c319-23. doi: 10.1159/000322830. Epub 2011 Feb 3. PMID: 21293154.

²⁷Munnangi S, Boktor SW. *Epidemiology Of Study Design*. 2021 Apr 29. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2022 Jan-. PMID: 29262004.

²⁸Daya S. Characteristics of good causation studies. *Semin Reprod Med*. 2003 Feb;21(1):73-83. doi: 10.1055/s-2003-39997. PMID: 12806562.

²⁹Vandenbroucke JP, Broadbent A, Pearce N. Causality and causal inference in epidemiology: the need for a pluralistic approach. *Int J Epidemiol*. 2016 Dec 1;45(6):1776-1786. doi: 10.1093/ije/dyv341. PMID: 26800751; PMCID: PMC5841832.

5. Conclusion

An index of independence very close to zero is of strong advantage in order to detect causal relationship in experimental and non-experimental (medical) research.

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Patient consent for publication

Not required.

Conflict of interest statement

No conflict of interest to declare.

Private note

The definition section of a paper need not and does not necessarily contain new scientific aspects. Above all, it also serves to better understand a scientific publication, to follow every step of the arguments of an author and to explain in greater details the fundamentals on which a publication is based. Therefore, there is no objective need to force authors to reinvent a scientific wheel once and again unless such a need appears obviously factually necessary. The effort to write about a certain subject in an original way in multiple publications does not exclude the necessity simply to cut and paste from an earlier work, and has nothing to do with self-plagiarism. However, such an attitude cannot simply be transferred to the sections' introduction, results, discussion and conclusions et cetera.

References

- Aristotle, William David Ross, and John Alexander Smith. *Volume VIII. Metaphysica*. The works of Aristotle. At The Clarendon Press, 1908. URL <http://archive.org/details/worksofaristotle12arisuoft>.
- A. J. Ayer. Negation. *The Journal of Philosophy*, 49(26):797–815, January 1952. doi: 10.2307/2020959. JSTOR.
- Monya Baker. 1,500 scientists lift the lid on reproducibility. *Nature*, 533(7604):452–454, 5 2016. ISSN 1476-4687. doi: 10.1038/533452a. PMID: 27225100.
- Carl Ludwig von Bar. *Die Lehre vom Kausalzusammenhang im Recht, besonders im Strafrecht*. Verlag von Bernhard Tauchnitz, Leipzig, 1871. URL http://dlib-pr.mpiar.mpg.de/m/kleioc/0010/exec/bigpage/%22101657_00000012.gif%22.
- Ilija Barukčić. *Die Kausalität*. Wiss.-Verl., Hamburg, 1. aufl. edition, January 1989. ISBN 3-9802216-0-1. ISBN: 978-3-9802216-0-1.
- Ilija Barukčić. *Die Kausalität*. Scientia, Wilhelmshaven, 2., völlig überarb. aufl. edition, January 1997. ISBN 3-9802216-4-4. ISBN: 978-3-9802216-4-1.
- Ilija Barukčić. *Causality: New statistical methods*. Books on Demand GmbH, Norderstedt, Germany, January 2005. ISBN 978-3-8334-3645-1.
- Ilija Barukčić. *Causality: New statistical methods*. Books on Demand GmbH, Norderstedt, Germany, January 2006a. ISBN 3-8334-3645-X. Deutsche Nationalbibliothek Frankfurt.
- Ilija Barukčić. Local hidden variable theorem. *Causation*, 1(1):11–17, Dec. 2006b. URL <https://www.causation.eu/index.php/causation/article/view/3>.
- Ilija Barukčić. Anti Heisenberg-Refutation Of Heisenberg's Uncertainty Relation. In *American Institute of Physics - Conference Proceedings*, volume 1327, pages 322–325, Linnaeus University, Växjö, Sweden, June 14 - 17, 2010, January 2011a. doi: 10.1063/1.3567453. AQT. Web of Science. Full text: [American Institute of Physics](#).
- Ilija Barukčić. The Equivalence of Time and Gravitational Field. *Physics Procedia*, 22:56–62, January 2011b. ISSN 18753892. doi: 10.1016/j.phpro.2011.11.008. ICPST 2011. Web of Science. Free full text: [Elsevier](#).
- Ilija Barukčić. Anti-Bell - Refutation of Bell's theorem: In: Quantum Theory: Reconsideration of Foundations-6 (QTRF6), Växjö, (Sweden), 11-14 June 2012. In *American Institute of Physics - Conference Proceedings*, volume 1508, pages 354–358, Växjö, Sweden, 2012. American Institute of Physics - Conference Proceedings. doi: 10.1063/1.4773147. QTRF 6. Web of Science. Full text: [American Institute of Physics](#).

- Ilija Barukčić. Anti Heisenberg – Refutation of Heisenberg’s Uncertainty Principle. *International Journal of Applied Physics and Mathematics*, 4(4):244–250, 2014. [IJAPM DOI: 10.7763/IJAPM.2014.V4.292](https://doi.org/10.7763/IJAPM.2014.V4.292).
- Ilija Barukčić. Anti Heisenberg—The End of Heisenberg’s Uncertainty Principle. *Journal of Applied Mathematics and Physics*, 04(05):881–887, 2016a. ISSN 2327-4352. [JAMP DOI: 10.4236/jamp.2016.45096](https://doi.org/10.4236/jamp.2016.45096).
- Ilija Barukčić. The Mathematical Formula of the Causal Relationship k. *International Journal of Applied Physics and Mathematics*, 6(2):45–65, January 2016b. doi: 10.17706/ijapm.2016.6.2.45-65. [IJAPM](https://doi.org/10.17706/ijapm.2016.6.2.45-65). Free full text: [IAP](https://doi.org/10.17706/ijapm.2016.6.2.45-65).
- Ilija Barukčić. Anti Bohr — Quantum Theory and Causality. *International Journal of Applied Physics and Mathematics*, 7(2):93–111, 2017a. doi: 10.17706/ijapm.2017.7.2.93-111. [IJAPM DOI: 10.17706/ijapm.2017.7.2.93-111](https://doi.org/10.17706/ijapm.2017.7.2.93-111).
- Ilija Barukčić. *Die Kausalität (1989)*. Books on Demand, Norderstedt, reprint edition, 2017b. ISBN 978-3-7448-1595-6. [ISBN-13: 9783744815956](https://www.isbn-international.org/product/9783744815956).
- Ilija Barukčić. *Theoriae causalitatis principia mathematica*. Books on Demand, Norderstedt, 2017c. ISBN 978-3-7448-1593-2. [ISBN-13: 9783754331347](https://www.isbn-international.org/product/9783754331347).
- Ilija Barukčić. Fusobacterium nucleatum —The Cause of Human Colorectal Cancer. *Journal of Biosciences and Medicines*, 06(03):31–69, 2018a. ISSN 2327-5081. doi: 10.4236/jbm.2018.63004.
- Ilija Barukčić. Human Papillomavirus—The Cause of Human Cervical Cancer. *Journal of Biosciences and Medicines*, 06(04):106–125, 2018b. ISSN 2327-5081. doi: 10.4236/jbm.2018.64009.
- Ilija Barukčić. Index of Independence. *Modern Health Science*, 2(2):1–25, 10 2019a. ISSN 2576-7305. doi: 10.30560/mhs.v2n2p1. URL <https://j.ideasspread.org/index.php/mhs/article/view/331>. [Modern Health Science](https://doi.org/10.30560/mhs.v2n2p1).
- Ilija Barukčić. Index of Unfairness. *Modern Health Science*, 2(1):22, 4 2019b. ISSN 2576-7305, 2576-7291. doi: 10.30560/mhs.v2n1p22. [Modern Health Science](https://doi.org/10.30560/mhs.v2n1p22).
- Ilija Barukčić. The P Value of likely extreme events. *International Journal of Current Science Research*, 5(11):1841–1861, 2019c. [IJCSR](https://www.ijcsr.in/) . Free full text: [ZENODO](https://zenodo.org/record/3333333).
- Ilija Barukčić. Causal relationship k. *International Journal of Mathematics Trends and Technology IJMTT*, 66(10):76–115, 2020a. URL <http://www.ijmttjournal.org/archive/ijmtt-v66i10p512>. Publisher: Seventh Sense Research Group SSRG.
- Ilija Barukčić. Locality and Non locality. *European Journal of Applied Physics*, 2(5):1–13, October 2020b. ISSN 2684-4451. doi: 10.24018/ejphysics.2020.2.5.22. URL <https://ej-physics.org/index.php/ejphysics/article/view/22>. Free full text: [EJAP](https://doi.org/10.24018/ejphysics.2020.2.5.22).
- Ilija Barukčić. *N-th index D-dimensional Einstein gravitational field equations. Geometry unchained.*, volume 1. Books on Demand GmbH, Hamburg-Norderstedt, 1 edition, 2020c. ISBN 978-3-7526-4490-6. [ISBN-13: 9783752644906](https://www.isbn-international.org/product/9783752644906) . Free full text (preprint): [ZENODO](https://zenodo.org/record/3333333).

- Ilija Barukčić. *Zero and infinity. Mathematics without frontiers*. Books on Demand GmbH, Hamburg-Norderstedt, 1 edition, 2020d. ISBN 978-3-7519-1873-2. ISBN-13: 9783751918732.
- Ilija Barukčić. Mutually exclusive events. *Causation*, 16(11):5–57, November 2021a. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.5746415. URL <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5746415>. Zenodo.
- Ilija Barukčić. Index of relationship. *Causation*, 16(8):5–37, April 2021b. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.5163179. URL <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5163179>. Zenodo.
- Ilija Barukčić. The logical content of the risk ratio. *Causation*, 16(4):5–41, February 2021c. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.4679509. Free full text: [Zenodo](#).
- Ilija Barukčić. The causal relationship k. *MATEC Web of Conferences*, 336:09032, 2021d. ISSN 2261-236X. doi: 10.1051/mateconf/202133609032. CSCNS2020. Web of Science. Free full text: [EDP Sciences](#).
- Ilija Barukčić and Okoh Ufuoma. *Analysis of Switching Resistive Circuits A Method Based on the Unification of Boolean and Ordinary Algebras*. Books on Demand, Norderstedt, first edition edition, 2020. ISBN 978-3-7519-8474-4. ISBN-13: 9783751984744.
- Barukčić, Ilija. Variance of binomial distribution. *Causation*, 17(1):5–22, 1 2022. URL <https://www.causation.eu/index.php/causation/article/view/7>.
- Jacobi Bernoulli. *Ars conjectandi, Opus posthumus: Accedit Tractatus de seriebus infinitis ; et epistola Gallice scripta De Ludo Pilae Reticularis*. Impensis Thurnisiorum [Tournes], fratrum, Basileae (Basel, Suisse), January 1713. doi: 10.3931/e-rara-9001. Free full text: [e-rara](#), [Zurich, CH](#).
- Alan Birnbaum. On the foundations of statistical inference: Binary experiments. *Annals of Mathematical Statistics*, 32(1):340–341, 1961. [jstor](#).
- Hubert M. Blalock. *Causal inferences in nonexperimental research*. Univ. of North Carolina Press, Chapel Hill, NC, 6. printing edition, 1972. ISBN 978-0-8078-0917-4.
- Ethan D. Bloch. *Proofs and fundamentals: a first course in abstract mathematics*. Springer, 2nd ed edition, 2011. ISBN 978-1-4419-7126-5.
- Niels Bohr. Causality and Complementarity. *Philosophy of Science*, 4(3):289–298, July 1937. ISSN 0031-8248, 1539-767X. doi: 10.1086/286465. URL http://www.informationphilosopher.com/solutions/scientists/bohr/Causality_and_Complementarity.pdf. Information-philosopher.
- George Boole. *An investigation of the laws of thought, on which are founded mathematical theories of logic and probabilities*. New York, Dover, 1854. Free full text: [archive.org](#), [San Francisco, CA 94118, USA](#).
- Max Born. Zur Quantenmechanik der Stoßvorgänge. *Zeitschrift für Physik*, 37(12):863–867, December 1926. ISSN 0044-3328. doi: 10.1007/BF01397477. URL <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01397477>.
- Auguste Bravais. Analyse mathématique sur les probabilités d es erreurs de situation d’un point.

Mémoires Présentées Par Divers Savants À L'Académie Royale Des Sciences De L'Institut De France, 9:255–332, January 1846.

Bundesanstalt für Strafsachen. *Entscheidungen des Bundesgerichtshofes*, volume 1 of *Entscheidungen des Bundesgerichtshofes*. Carl Heymanns Verlag, Detmold, 1951. URL <https://juris.bundesgerichtshof.de/cgi-bin/rechtsprechung/document.py?Gericht=bgh&Art=en&Datum=2008&Seite=99&nr=43553&pos=2985&anz=3634>.

K. C. Carter. Koch's postulates in relation to the work of Jacob Henle and Edwin Klebs. *Medical History*, 29(4):353–374, October 1985. ISSN 0025-7273. doi: 10.1017/s0025727300044689.

R. J. Cook and D. L. Sackett. The number needed to treat: a clinically useful measure of treatment effect. *BMJ (Clinical research ed.)*, 310(6977):452–454, 2 1995. ISSN 0959-8138. doi: 10.1136/bmj.310.6977.452. PMID: 7873954. Free full text: PMID: PMC2548824.

J. Cornfield. A method of estimating comparative rates from clinical data; applications to cancer of the lung, breast, and cervix. *Journal of the National Cancer Institute*, 11(6):1269–1275, 6 1951. ISSN 0027-8874. PMID: 14861651.

David Roxbee Cox. The regression analysis of binary sequences. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society. Series B (Methodological)*, 20(2):215–242, 1958. ISSN 0035-9246. JSTOR.

Harald Cramér. *Random variables and probability distributions*. Cambridge University Press, 1937.

A. P. Dempster. Causality and statistics. *Journal of Statistical Planning and Inference*, 25(3): 261–278, July 1990. ISSN 0378-3758. doi: 10.1016/0378-3758(90)90076-7. URL <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/0378375890900767>.

A. Einstein. Quanten-Mechanik Und Wirklichkeit. *Dialectica*, 2(3-4):320–324, 1948. ISSN 1746-8361. doi: 10.1111/j.1746-8361.1948.tb00704.x. URL <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/j.1746-8361.1948.tb00704.x>. *Dialectica*.

Ruiz Espejo. Review of Causality: New Statistical Methods, 2nd edn (by Ilija Barukcic; Books on Demand, Norderstedt DE, 2006): 34:1013-1014. *Journal of Applied Statistics*, 34(8):1011–1017, October 2007. doi: 10.1080/02664760701590707. URL <http://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/02664760701590707>.

William Feller. *Introduction to Probability Theory and its Applications. Volume I & II.*, volume 1. John Wiley and Sons Inc., 1st edition edition, 1 1950. John Wiley and Sons Inc.

Ronald Aylmer Fisher. On the Interpretation of Chi square from Contingency Tables, and the Calculation of P. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society*, 85(1):87–94, 1922. ISSN 0952-8385. doi: 10.2307/2340521. JSTOR.

Ronald Aylmer Fisher. The logic of inductive inference. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society*, 98 (1):39–82, 1935. ISSN 0952-8385. doi: 10.2307/2342435. JSTOR.

Ronald Aylmer Fisher. The negative binomial distribution. *Annals of Eugenics*, 11(1):182–187, 1941. ISSN 2050-1439. doi: 10.1111/j.1469-1809.1941.tb02284.x. Wiley Online Library.

Fisher, Ronald Aylmer. XV.—The Correlation between Relatives on the Supposition of Mendelian

Inheritance. *Earth and Environmental Science Transactions of The Royal Society of Edinburgh*, 52(2):399–433, 1919. ISSN 2053-5945. doi: 10.1017/S0080456800012163. [Royal Society of Edinburgh](#).

Eckart Förster and Yitzhak Y Melamed. “*Omnis determinatio est negatio*” – Determination, Negation and Self-Negation in Spinoza, Kant, and Hegel. In: *Spinoza and German idealism*. Eckart Forster & Yitzhak Y. Melamed (eds.). Cambridge University Press, Cambridge [England]; New York, 2012. ISBN 978-1-283-71468-6. URL <https://doi.org/10.1017/CB09781139135139>.

Francis Galton. Typical Laws of Heredity. *Nature*, 15(388):492–495, April 1877. ISSN 0028-0836, 1476-4687. doi: 10.1038/015492a0. URL <http://www.nature.com/articles/015492a0>.

Gauß, Carl Friedrich. *Theoria motus corporum coelestium in sectionibus conicis solem ambientium*. sumtibus Frid. Perthes et I. H. Besser, 1809. [e-rara, Zurich, CH](#).

H. T. Gonin. XIV. The use of factorial moments in the treatment of the hypergeometric distribution and in tests for regression. *The London, Edinburgh, and Dublin Philosophical Magazine and Journal of Science*, 21(139):215–226, January 1936. ISSN 1941-5982. doi: 10.1080/14786443608561573. [Taylor and Francis](#).

William Sealy Gosset. The probable error of a mean. *Biometrika*, 6(1):1–25, 1908. ISSN 0006-3444. doi: 1. [JSTOR](#).

William Sealy Gosset. The elimination of spurious correlation due to position in time or space. *Biometrika*, 10(1):179–180, 1914. ISSN 0006-3444. doi: 10.2307/2331746. [JSTOR](#).

Major Greenwood and G. Udny Yule. The statistics of anti-typhoid and anti-cholera inoculations, and the interpretation of such statistics in general. *Proceedings of the Royal Society of Medicine*, 8: 113–194, 6 1915. ISSN 0035-9157. doi: 10.1177/003591571500801433. PMID: 19978918. Free full text: [PMCID: PMC2004181](#).

J. B. S. Haldane. Karl Pearson, 1857-1957. Being a Centenary Lecture. *Biometrika*, 44(3/4):303–313, 1957. ISSN 0006-3444. doi: 10.2307/2332863. URL <https://www.jstor.org/stable/2332863>. [Biometrika Trust](#).

John Burdon Sanderson Haldane. The fitting of binomial distributions. *Annals of Eugenics*, 11(1): 179–181, 1941. ISSN 2050-1439. doi: 10.1111/j.1469-1809.1941.tb02283.x. [Wiley Online Library](#).

Hansemann, David Paul von. *Ueber das konditionale Denken in der Medizin und seine Bedeutung für die Praxis*. A. Hirschwald, Berlin, 1912. URL <https://catalogue.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/cb30574869t.public>.

Klaus Hedwig. Negatio negationis: Problemgeschichtliche Aspekte einer Denkstruktur. *Archiv für Begriffsgeschichte*, 24(1):7–33, 1980. ISSN 0003-8946. URL www.jstor.org/stable/24359358.

Hegel, Georg Wilhelm Friedrich. *Wissenschaft der Logik. Erster Band. Erstes Buch*. Johann Leonhard Schrag, Nürnberg, December 1812. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.5917182. URL <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5917182>. Online at: [Archive.org Zenodo](#).

Hegel, Georg Wilhelm Friedrich. *Wissenschaft der Logik. Erster Band. Zweites Buch*. Johann Leonhard

- Schrag, Nürnberg, December 1813. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.5919885. URL <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5919885>. Online at: [Archive.org Zenodo](#).
- Hegel, Georg Wilhelm Friedrich. *Wissenschaft der Logik. Zweiter Band*. Johann Leonhard Schrag, Nürnberg, December 1816. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.5920022. URL <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5920022>. Online at: [Archive.org Zenodo](#).
- Heinemann, Fritz H. The Meaning of Negation. *Proceedings of the Aristotelian Society*, 44:127–152, 1943. ISSN 0066-7374. [Oxford University Press](#).
- Heisenberg, Werner Karl. Über den anschaulichen Inhalt der quantentheoretischen Kinematik und Mechanik. *Zeitschrift für Physik*, 43(3):172–198, March 1927. ISSN 0044-3328. doi: 10.1007/BF01397280. URL <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01397280>.
- Friedrich Robert Helmert. Über die Wahrscheinlichkeit der Potenzsummen der Beobachtungsfehler und über einige damit im Zusammenhange stehende Fragen. *Zeitschrift für Mathematik und Physik*, 21(3):102–219, 1876.
- Friedrich Gustav Jacob Henle. *Von den Miasmen und Contagien und von den miasmatisch-contagiösen Krankheiten*. Verlag von August Hirschwald, Berlin, 1840. URL <https://doi.org/10.11588/diglit.15175>. [University Heidelberg urn:nbn:de:bsz:16-diglit-151756](#).
- Boris Hennig. The Four Causes. *The Journal of Philosophy*, 106(3):137–160, March 2009. doi: 10.5840/jphil200910634.
- Hessen, Johannes. *Das Kausalprinzip*. Verlag: Filser, Augsburg, 1928.
- Germund Hesslow. Two Notes on the Probabilistic Approach to Causality. *Philosophy of Science*, 43(2):290–292, June 1976. ISSN 0031-8248, 1539-767X. doi: 10.1086/288684. URL <https://www.journals.uchicago.edu/doi/10.1086/288684>.
- Germund Hesslow. Causality and Determinism. *Philosophy of Science*, 48(4):591–605, 1981. ISSN 0031-8248. URL <https://www.jstor.org/stable/186838>.
- Austin Bradford Hill. The environment and disease: association or causation? *Proceedings of the Royal Society of Medicine*, 58:295–300, January 1965.
- Holbach, Paul Henri Thiry Baron de. *Système de la nature, ou des lois du monde physique et du monde moral. Première partie*. Par Jean Baptiste de Mirabaud, Londres, 1770. URL <https://doi.org/10.3931/e-rara-14756>. [Zenodo](#).
- Laurence R. Horn. *A natural history of negation*. University of Chicago Press, Chicago, 1989. ISBN 978-0-226-35337-1. URL <https://emilkirkegaard.dk/en/wp-content/uploads/A-natural-history-of-negation-Laurence-R.-Horn.pdf>.
- Christiaan Huygens and Frans van Schooten. *De ratiociniis in ludo alae: In: Exercitationum mathematicarum liber primus [- quintus]*. ex officina Johannis Elsevirii, Lugdunum Batavorum (Leiden, The Netherlands), January 1657. doi: 10.3931/e-rara-8813. Free full text: [e-rara, Zurich, CH](#).
- Justice Matthews, Mr. Hayes, by next Friend, v. Michigan Central R. Co., 111 U.S. 228, 1884. Argued March 19, 1884. Decided April 7. *U. S. Supreme Court*, 1884. [U. S. Supreme Court, 1884](#).

- Michal Kicinski, David A. Springate, and Evangelos Kontopantelis. Publication bias in meta-analyses from the cochrane database of systematic reviews. *Statistics in Medicine*, 34(20):2781–2793, 9 2015. ISSN 1097-0258. doi: 10.1002/sim.6525. PMID: 25988604.
- Mirjam J. Knol. Down with odds ratios: risk ratios in cohort studies and randomised clinical trials (article in dutch). *Nederlands Tijdschrift Voor Geneeskunde*, 156(28):A4775, 2012. ISSN 1876-8784. PMID: 22805792.
- Anton Friedrich Koch. Die Selbstbeziehung der Negation in Hegels Logik. *Zeitschrift für philosophische Forschung*, 53(1):1–29, 1999. ISSN 0044-3301. URL www.jstor.org/stable/20484868.
- Robert Koch. Neue Untersuchungen über die Mikroorganismen bei infektiösen Wundkrankheiten. *Deutsche Medizinische Wochenschrift*, 4(43):531–533, 1878. Zenodo.
- Kolmogoroff, Andreï Nikolaevich. *Grundbegriffe der Wahrscheinlichkeitsrechnung*. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg, January 1933. ISBN 978-3-642-49596-0. Springer.
- Kolmogorov, Andreï Nikolaevich. *Foundations of the theory of probability*. Translated by Nathan Morrison. Chelsea Publishing Company, 1950. ISBN 978-0-486-82159-7. archive.org, San Francisco, CA 94118, USA.
- Korch, Helmut. *Das Problem der Kausalität*. Dt. Verlag der Wissenschaften, Berlin, 1965.
- Günter Kröber. Der Konditionalismus und seine Kritik in der sowjetischen Wissenschaft. *Wissenschaftliche Zeitschrift der Karl-Marx Universität Leipzig*, 10(2):137–153, 1961.
- Kenneth Kunen. Negation in logic programming. *The Journal of Logic Programming*, 4(4):289–308, December 1987. ISSN 0743-1066. doi: 10.1016/0743-1066(87)90007-0. URL <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/0743106687900070>.
- Harold Langsam. Kant, Hume, and Our Ordinary Concept of Causation. *Philosophy and Phenomenological Research*, 54(3):625, September 1994. ISSN 00318205. doi: 10.2307/2108584. URL <https://www.jstor.org/stable/2108584?origin=crossref>.
- Pierre Simon de LaPlace. *Théorie analytique des probabilités*. Courcier, 1 1812. e-rara, Zurich, CH.
- Andreas Laupacis, David L. Sackett, and Robin S. Roberts. An assessment of clinically useful measures of the consequences of treatment. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 318(26):1728–1733, 1988. doi: 10.1056/NEJM198806303182605. PMID: 3374545. NEJM.
- D. Massel and M. K. Cruickshank. The number remaining at risk: an adjunct to the number needed to treat. *The Canadian Journal of Cardiology*, 18(3):254–258, 3 2002. ISSN 0828-282X. PMID: 11907613.
- Abraham de Moivre. *The Doctrine of Chances or a Method of Calculating the Probability of Events in Play*. printed by W. Pearson for the author, London, January 1718. doi: 10.3931/e-rara-10420. Free full text: e-rara, Zurich, CH.
- Jürgen Neffe. *Einstein: A Biography*. Farrar, Straus and Giroux, New York (USA), 2006.
- Russell Newstadt. *Omnis Determinatio est Negatio: A Genealogy and Defense of the Hegelian Con-*

ception of Negation. Loyola University Chicago, Chicago (IL), dissertation edition, 2015. Free full text: [Loyola University Chicago, USA](#).

Jerzy Neyman and Egon Sharpe Pearson. IX. On the problem of the most efficient tests of statistical hypotheses. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London. Series A, Containing Papers of a Mathematical or Physical Character*, 231(694–706):289–337, 2 1933. ISSN 0264-3952, 2053-9258. doi: 10.1098/rsta.1933.0009. [The Royal Society, London, GB](#).

Jean George Pierre Nicod. A reduction in the number of primitive propositions of logic. *Proceedings of the Cambridge Philosophical Society*, 19:32–41, 1917.

Jean George Pierre Nicod. Les relations des valeurs et les relations de sens en logique formelle. *Revue de métaphysique et de morale*, 31:467–480, 1924.

Judea Pearl. *Causality: models, reasoning, and inference*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, U.K. ; New York, 2000. ISBN 978-0-521-89560-6.

Karl Pearson. III. Contributions to the Mathematical Theory of Evolution. On the Dissection of Asymmetrical-Frequency Curves. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London, Series A*, 185:71–85, 1894. [The Royal Society](#).

Karl Pearson. VII. Mathematical contributions to the theory of evolution.—III. Regression, heredity, and panmixia. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London. Series A, Containing Papers of a Mathematical or Physical Character*, 187:253–318, January 1896. doi: 10.1098/rsta.1896.0007. URL <https://royalsocietypublishing.org/doi/abs/10.1098/rsta.1896.0007>.

Karl Pearson. XV. On certain properties of the hypergeometrical series, and on the fitting of such series to observation polygons in the theory of chance. *The London, Edinburgh, and Dublin Philosophical Magazine and Journal of Science*, 47(285):236–246, January 1899. ISSN 1941-5982. doi: 10.1080/14786449908621253. [Taylor and Francis](#).

Karl Pearson. X. On the criterion that a given system of deviations from the probable in the case of a correlated system of variables is such that it can be reasonably supposed to have arisen from random sampling. *The London, Edinburgh, and Dublin Philosophical Magazine and Journal of Science*, 50(302):157–175, July 1900. ISSN 1941-5982. doi: 10.1080/14786440009463897. [Taylor and Francis](#).

Karl Pearson. III. Mathematical contributions to the theory of evolution. — XII. On a generalised Theory of alternative Inheritance, with special reference to Mendel's laws. *p 66: Standard dev binomial distribution*, 203(359–371):53–86, 1 1904a. doi: 10.1098/rsta.1904.0015. [Royal Society](#).

Karl Pearson. *Mathematical contributions to the theory of evolution. XIII. On the theory of contingency and its relation to association and normal correlation*. Biometric Series I. Dulau and Co., London, January 1904b. Free full text: [archive.org, San Francisco, CA 94118, USA](#).

Josiah Royce. *Negation*, volume 9 of *Encyclopaedia of Religion and Ethics*. J. Hastings (ed.). Charles Scribner's Sons, New York (USA), 1917. Free full text: [archive.org, San Francisco, CA 94118, USA](#).

- Sackett, DL and Deeks, JJ and Altman, DG. Down with odds ratios! *Evidence-Based Med.*, 1:164–166, 1996. *.pdf file DOI: [10.1136/ebm.1996.1.164](https://doi.org/10.1136/ebm.1996.1.164).
- D. A. Sadowsky, A. G. Gilliam, and J. Cornfield. The statistical association between smoking and carcinoma of the lung. *Journal of the National Cancer Institute*, 13(5):1237–1258, 4 1953. ISSN 0027-8874. PMID: [13035448](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/13035448/).
- Schlick, Friedrich Albert Moritz. Die Kausalität in der gegenwärtigen Physik. *Naturwissenschaften*, 19:145–162, 2 1931. ISSN 0028-1042. doi: [10.1007/BF01516406](https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01516406). Springer.
- Schrödinger, Erwin Rudolf Josef Alexander. An undulatory theory of the mechanics of atoms and molecules. *Physical Review*, 28:1049–1070, Dec 1926. doi: [10.1103/PhysRev.28.1049](https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRev.28.1049). URL <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRev.28.1049>.
- Schrödinger, Erwin Rudolf Josef Alexander. Was ist ein Naturgesetz? *Naturwissenschaften*, 17(1): 9–11, January 1929. ISSN 1432-1904. doi: [10.1007/BF01505758](https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01505758). URL <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01505758>.
- Schrödinger, Erwin Rudolf Josef Alexander. Are there quantum jumps? *British Journal for the Philosophy of Science*, 3(11):233–242, 1952. doi: [10.1093/bjps/III.11.233](https://doi.org/10.1093/bjps/III.11.233).
- Henry Maurice Sheffer. A set of five independent postulates for boolean algebras, with application to logical constants. *Transactions of the American Mathematical Society*, 14(4):481–488, 1913. ISSN 0002-9947, 1088-6850. doi: [10.1090/S0002-9947-1913-1500960-1](https://doi.org/10.1090/S0002-9947-1913-1500960-1). Free full text: archive.org, San Francisco, CA 94118, USA.
- E. Sober. Venetian Sea Levels, British Bread Prices, and the Principle of the Common Cause. *The British Journal for the Philosophy of Science*, 52(2):331–346, January 2001. ISSN 0007-0882. DOI: [10.1093/bjps/52.2.331](https://doi.org/10.1093/bjps/52.2.331).
- J. L. Speranza and Laurence R. Horn. A brief history of negation. *Journal of Applied Logic*, 8(3): 277–301, September 2010. ISSN 1570-8683. DOI: [10.1016/j.jal.2010.04.001](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jal.2010.04.001) ScienceDirect.
- Patrick Suppes. *A probabilistic theory of causality*. Number Fasc. 24 in Acta philosophica Fennica. North-Holland Pub. Co, Amsterdam, 1970. ISBN 978-0-7204-2404-1.
- M. E. Thompson. Ilija Barukčić. Causality. New Statistical Methods. A Book Review. *International Statistical Institute - Short Book Review*, 26(01):6, January 2006. ISI - Short Book Reviews, p. 6.
- author Unknown. Kausale und konditionale Weltanschauung. *Nature*, 90(2261):698–699, February 1913. ISSN 1476-4687. doi: [10.1038/090698a0](https://doi.org/10.1038/090698a0). URL <https://www.nature.com/articles/090698a0>. Number: 2261 Publisher: Nature Publishing Group.
- J. v. Uspensky. *Introduction To Mathematical Probability*. McGraw-Hill Company, New York (USA), 1937. Free full text: archive.org, San Francisco, CA 94118, USA.
- Max Verworn. *Kausale und konditionale Weltanschauung*. Verlag von Gustav Fischer, Jena, 1912.
- Michael V. Wedin. Negation and quantification in aristotle. *History and Philosophy of Logic*, 11(2):131–150, January 1990. ISSN 0144-5340. doi: [10.1080/01445349008837163](https://doi.org/10.1080/01445349008837163). DOI: [10.1080/01445349008837163](https://doi.org/10.1080/01445349008837163).

William Allen Whitworth. *Choice and Chance. With 1000 Exercises*. Deighton, Bell & Co., fifth edition edition, 1901. archive.org, San Francisco, CA 94118, USA .

John Woods and Douglas Walton. Post Hoc, Ergo Propter Hoc. *The Review of Metaphysics*, 30(4): 569–593, 1977. ISSN 0034-6632. URL <https://www.jstor.org/stable/20126985>.

Frank Yates. Contingency Tables Involving Small Numbers and the Chi square Test. *Supplement to the Journal of the Royal Statistical Society*, 1(2):217–235, 1934. ISSN 1466-6162. doi: 10.2307/2983604. [JSTOR](http://www.jstor.org).

George Udny Yule. On the methods of measuring association between two attributes. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society*, 75(6):579–652, 1912. ISSN 0952-8385. doi: 10.2307/2340126. [JSTOR](http://www.jstor.org).

George Udny Yule and Karl Pearson. VII. On the association of attributes in statistics: with illustrations from the material of the childhood society. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London. Series A, Containing Papers of a Mathematical or Physical Character*, 194(252–261): 257–319, 1 1900. doi: 10.1098/rsta.1900.0019. [The Royal Society, London, GB](http://www.royalsocietypublishing.org).

Patrick Manuel Zesar. *nihil fit sine causa - Die Kausalität im Spanischen und Portugiesischen: DIPLOMARBEIT. Magister der Philosophie*. Universität Wien, Wien, January 2013. URL http://othes.univie.ac.at/25095/1/2013-01-22_0506065.pdf.

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I was born on October, 1st 1961 in Novo Selo, Bosnia and Herzegovina, former Yugoslavia. I am of Croatian origin. From 1982-1989 C.E., I studied human medicine at the University of Hamburg, Germany. Meanwhile, I am working as a specialist of internal medicine. My basic field of research since my high school days at the Wirtschaftsgymnasium Bruchsal, Baden Württemberg, Germany is the mathematization of the relationship between a cause and an effect valid without any restriction under any circumstances including the conditions of classical logic, probability theory, quantum mechanics, special and general theory of relativity, human medicine et cetera. I endeavour to investigate positions of quantum mechanics, relativity theory, mathematics et cetera, only insofar as these positions put into question or endanger **the general validity of the principle of causality**.

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ⁿ<https://portal.dnb.de/opac/showNextResultSite?currentResultId=%22Barukcic%22%26any¤tPosition=30>